

The Cenozoic Pickworthiidae of the European Atlantic Region (Mollusca, Gastropoda, Caenogastropoda)

Los Pickworthiidae cenozoicos de la región atlántica europea (Mollusca, Gastropoda, Caenogastropoda)

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ABSTRACT

Thirty-one species of Pickworthiidae from the Paleocene to Neogene of the European Atlantic region are recorded (including one Mediterranean Pliocene species). Seventeen species are described as new to science and two are unnamed. Four species are known from the Paleocene; two of them are new (*Mareleptopoma? alicae* n. sp., *Sansonia schnefferi* n. sp.). Fourteen species are known from the Eocene. Among them, two are from the Lower Eocene, three from the Middle Eocene (of which two are new species: *Gania gougeroti* n. sp. and *Gania fossaroides* n. sp.), and ten from the Upper Eocene (of which eight are new species: *Gania canhotensis* n. sp., *Gania granulosa* n. sp., *Gania laevigata* n. sp., *Gania priaboniana* n. sp., *Mareleptopoma orbum* n. sp., *Sansonia orthensis* n. sp., *Sansonia aturensis* n. sp., *Sansonia imperforata* n. sp.). Two species are recognized from the Lower Oligocene (one unnamed) and six from the Upper Oligocene of which five are new species: *Clatrosansonia praelapugyensis* n. sp., *Clatrosansonia luporadensis* n. sp., *Gania marconensis* n. sp., *Gania peirahoradensis* n. sp., *Microliotia imperfecta* n. sp. Three species are reported from the Lower Miocene including *Astrosansonia micraster*. This species was previously known only from the Middle Miocene of the Paratethys. *Mareleptopoma lychoviense* is recognized from the Lower Eocene to the Middle Miocene. It represents 74% of the recorded specimens. Higher diversity is reported in the Priabonian deposits where seven species occur in a single outcrop. The species have been predominantly collected from a restricted area of the Adour Basin (SW France) in a North Pyrenean Trough (Eocene) or in a paleo-canyon (Oligocene-Neogene). They are a good example of fossil distribution which is severely facies-dependent; the poor fossil records are probably an artefact due to the sparse habitat of this cryptic family. Finally, a species of Pickworthiidae is reported for the first time from the Miocene of the New World, *Mareleptopoma toriferens* Janssen, 2004 is transferred to the genus *Gania*, and the relocation of *Mareleptopoma verdense* Rolán & Rubio, 1999 to *Chrystella* is rebutted.

RESUMEN

Se registran treinta y una especies de Pickworthiidae del Paleoceno al Neógeno de la región atlántica europea (incluida una especie del Plioceno mediterráneo). Diecisiete especies se describen como nuevas para la ciencia y dos más no se nombran. Se conocen cuatro especies del Paleoceno; dos de ellas nuevas (*Mareleptopoma? alicae* n. sp.,

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Sansonia schnetleri n. sp.). Hay catorce especies del Eoceno, dos de ellas del Eoceno Inferior, tres del Eoceno Medio (de las cuales dos son especies nuevas: *Gania gougeroti* n. sp. y *Gania fossaroides* n. sp.), y diez del Eoceno Superior (de las cuales ocho son especies nuevas: *Gania canhotensis* n. sp., *Gania granulosa* n. sp., *Gania laevigata* n. sp., *Gania priaboniana* n. sp., *Mareleptopoma orbum* n. sp., *Sansonia orthensis* n. sp., *Sansonia aturensis* n. sp., *Sansonia imperforata* n. sp.). Se reconocen dos especies del Oligoceno Inferior (una sin darle nombre) y seis del Oligoceno Superior de las cuales cinco son especies nuevas: *Clatrosansonia praelapugyensis* n. sp., *Clatrosansonia luporadens* n. sp., *Gania marconensis* n. sp., *Gania peirahoradensis* n. sp., *Microliotia imperfecta* n. sp.). Se reportan tres especies del Mioceno Inferior, incluida *Astrosansonia micraster* que se conocía anteriormente sólo en el Mioceno Medio de la Paratethys. *Mareleptopoma lychoviense* se reconoce desde el Eoceno Inferior hasta el Mioceno Medio y representa el 74% de los ejemplares registrados. Se documenta una mayor diversidad en los depósitos del Priaboniano, donde siete especies se encuentran en un solo afloramiento. Las especies han sido recolectadas predominantemente en un área restringida de la cuenca del Adour (SO de Francia) en una depresión del norte de los Pirineos (Eoceno) o en un paleocañón (Oligoceno-Neógeno). Son un buen ejemplo de distribución de fósiles que depende en gran medida de las facies; Los registros fósiles pobres son probablemente un artefacto debido al escaso hábitat de esta críptica familia. Finalmente, se reporta por primera vez una especie de Pickworthiidae del Mioceno del Nuevo Mundo, se reubica *Mareleptopoma toriferens* Janssen, 2004 en el género *Gania*, y se rechaza la reubicación de *Mareleptopoma verdense* Rolán & Rubio, 1999 en el género *Chrystellia*.

KEY WORDS: Aquitaine Basin, cryptic environment, *Astrosansonia*, *Gania*, *Clatrosansonia*, *Mareleptopoma*, *Microliotia*, *Sansonia*, *Faxia*, Eocene, Oligocene.

PALABRAS CLAVE: cuenca de Aquitania, ambiente críptico, *Astrosansonia*, *Gania*, *Clatrosansonia*, *Mareleptopoma*, *Microliotia*, *Sansonia*, *Faxia*, Eoceno, Oligoceno.

INTRODUCTION

The family Pickworthiidae was relatively recently investigated (BOUCHET & LE RENARD 1988; KASE 1998a-c, 1999; KASE & RAINES 2017; LE RENARD & BOUCHET 2003; JANSSEN 2004). All the Recent species are recorded from tropical provinces except *Mareleptoma iredalei* (Bavay, 1920) which extends to the warm-temperate region in Northwest Pacific (HASEGAWA in OKUTANI 2000). The majority of the species are known from the Indo-West-Pacific, a small number is from the Caribbean and only one species is known in the West-African province. At the beginning of the 1980s only the genus, *Sansonia*, was recognized (RAFFI & TAVIANI 1985) and this group was thought to be a bathyal taxon. In fact, more than 70% of the Recent species were described after 1990 (LE RENARD & BOUCHET 2003) particularly due to the

exploration of submarine caves (KASE 1998a-c, 1999) which appears to be the preferred habitat of the family.

For a long time the phylogenetic relationship of the Pickworthiidae remained uncertain because most of the species are only known from empty shells. The unique taenioglossate radula (LE RENARD & BOUCHET 2003) and the Cerithioidean type animal itself (Fig. 1) observed during the Panglao workshop in the Philippines (BOUCHET 2009) did not allow for a conclusive allocation to a superfamily. Based on the similarity of the protoconch, the Pickworthiidae were placed within Littorinoidea by REID (1998). The Sherborniinae have been included as subfamilies of Pickworthiidae by BOUCHET & ROCROI (2005). They contain the genera *Sherbornia* and *Faxia*. The position of the fossil genera *Faxia*

Figure 1. *Discrevinia* sp. (H= 2 mm) collected during the Panglao Marine Biodiversity Project 2004. Bohol Island, Cortes Takot, Stn. S15, 9°41.3'N - 123°49.5'E, 4 m. Photo by P. Lozouet.

Figura 1. *Discrevinia* sp. (H= 2 mm) recolectados durante el Proyecto de Biodiversidad Marina de Panglao 2004. Isla Bohol, Cortes Takot, Est. S15, 9°41,3'N - 123°49,5'E, 4 m. Foto de P. Lozouet.

[Faxiidae, RAVN, 1933] was questionable but the observation of well-preserved protoconchs shows that it is clearly of Pickworthiidae type and thus *Faxia* is included in this revision. The Pelyciidinae, with a single genus, *Pelycidion*, have been only tentatively included as a subfamily within the Pickworthiidae (BOUCHET & ROCROI 2005).

The paper by TAKANO & KANO (2014) sheds new light on the Pickworthiidae which appear related to the Cerithioidea. Another aspect of this paper, the Pelyciidinae and the Pickworthiidae/*Microliotia* constitute a monophyletic group with the Cerithioidea. In contrast, *Mareleptopoma iredalei*, one of the most common species of Pickworthiidae, is excluded from this clade. The paraphyletic nature of the Pickworthiidae which emerges now needs to be confirmed. The work of TAKANO & KANO (2014) focused on the systematic position of the parasitic family Eulimidae and not on the position of the Pickworthiidae (only three species were included). Therefore we conserve the classic systematic treatment of this group (Le RENARD & BOUCHET 2003;

MOLLUSCABASE (2023). Thus defined, the Pickworthiidae comprise 14 genera (of which two are only known from fossils: *Gania* and *Faxia*) and 70 Recent species (MOLLUSCABASE 2023).

The fossil record of the Pickworthiidae is poor. About fifteen fossil species are known, of which nine have been described from the Middle Miocene (Badenian) of Paratethys (JANSSEN 2004). The oldest undoubted Pickworthiidae are recorded from the Paleocene of Denmark. Only one species has been described from the Eocene and one from the Oligocene and Lower Miocene. In an attempt to re-evaluate the biodiversity of the molluscan fauna from the Paleogene to Miocene of the French Atlantic coast, much new data has been collected (LOZOUET 2014). Among them, several new species of Pickworthiidae were recognized and appear to be precious benchmarks in our understanding for the knowledge of this family. Noteworthy, Middle Miocene species of Paratethys, revisited by JANSSEN (2004), have been included in order to present an overview of the Pickworthiidae of the European Cenozoic.

Figure 2. Location of the fossil outcrops in the Aquitaine Basin.
 Figura 2. Localización de los afloramientos fósiles en la cuenca de Aquitania.

GEOGRAPHIC AND STRATIGRAPHIC SETTING

Figure 2 indicates the locations of the collecting sites. The stratigraphic occurrence of the material examined ranges from the Paleocene to the base of

the Neogene. All the Paleocene species were collected in the Fakse site (Denmark) and the majority of Paleogene and Neogene species were collected in the south of the Aquitaine Basin in the Adour subbasin. In fact, except for *Gania gougeroti*, the Aquitaine

species were all collected in a narrow geographical area from north of Dax to south of Peyrehorade (Fig. 2).

The Neogene sites include on the one hand, the purely very littoral Aquitanian deposits of St-Paul-lès-Dax and the Burdigalian site of Mimbaste (east of Dax), and on the other hand, the marly deposits from the Upper Burdigalian of the erosional paleo-canyon of Saubrigues (south of Dax).

The sites from the Upper Oligocene are also divided into two sets, 1) the outcrops with purely littoral facies from St-Paul-lès-Dax and Pontonx (generally limestone sand, sometimes marl with many hermatypic corals), 2) the marly outcrops of the paleo-canyon of Saubrigues with circalittoral to upper bathyal facies. Two sites from the Lower Oligocene (Rupelian), located to the south of Dax (Gaas and Orist) and with a very littoral facies, have yielded two species of Pickworthiidae.

The Eocene outcrops of Aquitaine are located in the North Pyrenean Trough. They are essentially marl or clay deposits of circalittoral to bathyal facies. From an environment point of view, they are similar to the Upper Oligocene deposits of the Saubrigues paleo-canyon. The Priabonian and Lutetian deposits are exposed in the vicinity of Peyrehorade and the Lower Eocene deposits in the vicinity of Pau. The chronology of the various sites was described by NOLF (1988), and NOLF *ET AL.* (2002) for the Eocene and by CAHUZAC *ET AL.* (1995) and LOZOUET (1998) for the Oligocene and the Neogene.

The Baron outcrop has yielded the richest Bartonian molluscan fauna of the Paris Basin (DOLIN *ET AL.* 1980) and the only species of Pickworthiidae known in this Basin. The cross-stratified coarse sands with pebble beds, called in the local terminology "*faciès charrié*", indicate accumulation in shallow water of a depth of 0-10 m.

In the Paleocene quarry of Fakse, a small town situated in Eastern Zealand (Denmark), these micro-molluscs are collected only in an unconsolidated coral

limestone (named nose-chalk) in which aragonitic mollusc shells are preserved due to transformation into calcite. The rich fauna of the "nose-chalk" contains many elements from cryptic environments and was compared (SCHNETLER *ET AL.* 2001) with the Peyrère fauna (Upper Oligocene of Adour basin).

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Since the 1970s, we have sampled a large number of localities from the Paleogene and Neogene of the French Atlantic with a stratigraphic range from the early Paleogene to the Late Miocene. The material examined in this study is part of this large collection. Additional material was collected by Kai I. Schnetler from the Paleocene of Denmark.

For the marl deposits of the Adour Basin, large samples of about 300 kg to 1000 kg were collected. After treatment (i.e. drying and rinsing several times) the samples were sieved in fresh water with no additives through mesh sieves of 1 cm to 0.4 mm. The finer fractions were sorted with the aid of a dissecting microscope.

Abbreviations used:

- Shell Height (H)= the maximum dimension parallel to the axis of coiling.
- Shell Breadth (B)= the maximum dimension perpendicular to H.
- H/B= height to breadth ratio.
- Axial ribs or costulae are counted on the penultimate whorl.
- ISL Kai Ingemann Schnetler collection, Langå, Denmark.
- MGUH Type collection of the Statens Naturhistoriske Museum (SNM), Copenhagen, Denmark.
- MNHN-IM *Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle* (Paris), collection de Malacologie
- MNHN.F. *Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle* (Paris), collection de Paléontologie
- SMF *Forschungsinstitut und Naturmuseum Senckenberg, Frankfurt*
- spm= (fossil) specimen.

SYSTEMATICS

Class GASTROPODA Cuvier, 1795
Subclass CAENOGASTROPODA Cox, 1960
Superfamily CERITHIOIDEA J. Fleming, 1822
Family PICKWORTHIIDAE Iredale, 1917
Subfamily PICKWORTHIINAE Iredale, 1917
Genus *Astrosansonia* Le Renard & Bouchet, 2003

Type species: *Liotia dautzenbergi* Bavay, 1917 (by original designation).

Astrosansonia micraster (Boettger, 1907) (Fig. 3)

Liotia micraster Boettger, 1907: 189.

Liotia micraster Boettger – ZILCH, 1934: 205, pl. 3 fig. 52a-c.

Astrosansonia micraster (Boettger) – LE RENARD & BOUCHET, 2003: 588.

Astrosansonia micraster (Boettger) – JANSSEN, 2004: 264, pl. 5 fig. 12.

Material examined: FRANCE • 13 spm.; St-Jean-de-Marsacq (Lahitet); Lower Miocene, Burdigalian; Lozouet leg.; MNHN.F.A88439 to A88443 • 11 spm.; St-Martin-de-Hinx (La Montagne); Lower Miocene, Burdigalian; Lozouet leg.; MNHN • 6 spm.; St-Martin-de-Hinx (Lanot); Lower Miocene, Burdigalian; Lozouet leg.; MNHN.

Remarks: *A. micraster* was only known from the lower part of the Middle Miocene (Badenian) of the Paratethys (BOETTGER 1907). It is very similar to the Recent species *A. dautzenbergi* (Bavay, 1917) from Polynesia. It

was considered to be one of the species demonstrating a distribution/range restricted to the Paratethys domain and the pre-Indo-West-Pacific before the final closure of the Tethyan seaway at about 17-18 My.

Genus *Clatrosansonia* Sabelli & Taviani, 2003

Type species: *Mecoliotia philippina* Bandel & Kowalke, 1997 (by original designation), Recent.

Clatrosansonia luporadens n. sp. (Figs. 4A-F)

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Type material. *Holotype:* FRANCE • 1 spm.; St-Paul-lès-Dax (Estoti); Upper Oligocene, Chattian; Lozouet leg.; MNHN.F.A88444.

Type locality and stage: St-Paul-lès-Dax (Estoti), Landes; Upper Oligocene (Chattian).

Etymology: From Latin, dedicated to Sylvestre Grateloup (who described the first fossil molluscs from the type locality), Grateloup means literally “scratch the wolf”.

Description: Shell very small, turbinate, consisting of 3 ¹/₄ whorls of teleoconch, angular, separated by a channelled suture. Protoconch bulbous (worn in the holotype), consisting of approximately 2 ¹/₂ convex whorls, tilted relative to the axis of the teleo-

conch, ending in a deep sinusigera notch bordered by a recurved lip; protoconch I smooth, protoconch II with 5-6 cords still visible including two distinctly strongest; strong adapical cord continuing as a carina to the sinusigera lip. Sculpture on the spire consisting of

Figure 3. *Astrosansonia micraster* (Boettger, 1907), Upper Burdigalian. A: Saint-Jean-de-Marsacq (Lahitet) [MNHN.FA88439], Dmax= 1.1 mm; B: same locality [MNHN.FA88440], Dmax= 1.1 mm; C: Saint-Martin-de-Hinx (Secat) [MNHN.FA88442], Dmax= 1.2 mm; D, E: same locality [MNHN.FA88443], Dmax= 1.2 mm; F, G: Saint-Martin-de-Hinx (La Montagne) [MNHN.FA88441], Dmax= 1.2 mm. SEM micrographs by J. Le Renard.

Figura 3. *Astrosansonia micraster* (Boettger, 1907), Burdigaliense superior. A: Saint-Jean-de-Marsacq (Lahitet) [MNHN.FA88439], Dmáx= 1,1 mm; B: misma localidad [MNHN.FA88440], Dmax= 1,1 mm; C: Saint-Martin-de-Hinx (Secat) [MNHN.FA88442], Dmáx= 1,2 mm; D, E: misma localidad [MNHN.FA88443], Dmax= 1,2 mm; F, G: Saint-Martin-de-Hinx (La Montagne) [MNHN.FA88441], Dmax= 1,2 mm. Micrografías electrónicas de barrido por J. Le Renard.

three spiral cords crossed by 22 axial ribs, granulated at their intersections and forming a regular square mesh; the first cord is located along the adapical suture, the second in a median position, the third above the abapical suture. Body whorl angular, occupies 69% of total length of shell. Base with 9 regularly spaced cords including one robust cord surrounding the umbilical depression and forming a strip at the abapical part; rather narrow but deep umbilicus.

Aperture strongly prosocline with thick peristome forming a flattened disc with 7 concentric rings; outer lip thickened by broad varix. Cords of body whorls reaching outer lip. Micro-sculpture: teleoconch studded, with minute, spirally aligned granules in the interstices of spiral cords and axial ribs.

Size (holotype): H= 1.2 mm; Dmax= 1 mm.

Remarks: This is the oldest known species of the genus *Clatrosansonia*. Com-

pared with *Clatrosansonia lapugyensis* and *C. praelapugyensis*, it has a more angular base, a narrower umbilicus surrounded by a cord forming a strip. In addition, there are 9 cords on the base of *C. luporadens* versus 6 on *C. praelapugyensis*. *Clatrosansonia luporadens* likewise resembles

the type species of *Clatrosansonia*, *C. philippina* (Bandel & Kowalke, 1997) from the Indo-Pacific, but differs in having a body whorl with a less projecting cord. Finally, *C. luporadens* is angulated by a strong median cord; in *C. philippina*, the whorls are almost straight.

Clatrosansonia praelapugyensis n. sp. (Figs. 4G-M)

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Type material. *Holotype*: FRANCE • 1 spm.; St-Paul-lès-Dax (Abesse “Falaise”); Upper Oligocene, Chattian; Lozouet leg.; MNHN.F.A88445.

Type locality and stage: St-Paul-lès-Dax (Abesse “Falaise”), Landes; Upper Oligocene (Chattian).

Other material examined: FRANCE • 1 spm.; St-Martin-de-Hinx (Lanot); Lower Miocene, Burdigalian; Lozouet leg.; MNHN.

Etymology: The probable ancestor of *C. lapugyensis* from the middle Miocene.

Description: Shell very small, turbinate, consisting of 2 ¹/₄ whorls of teleoconch, separated by a channelled suture. Protoconch unknown. Sculpture on the spire of the teleoconch consisting of three spiral cords crossed by 26 axial ribs (penultimate whorl), slightly granulated at their intersections and forming a regular square mesh; the first cord is located along the adapical suture, the second in a median position, the third above the abapical suture. Body whorl evenly convex, large. Base with 6 regularly spaced cords including one, robust, around large and deep umbilicus. Aperture strongly prosocline with thick peristome forming a flattened disc with 4-5 concentric rings; outer lip thickened by broad varix. Cords of body whorls reaching outer lip. Micro-sculp-

ture: teleoconch studded, with minute, spirally aligned granules in the interstices of spiral cords and axial ribs.

Size (holotype): H= 0.9 mm; Dmax= 0.95 mm.

Remarks: Compared with the holotype of *Clatrosansonia praelapugyensis* from the Upper Oligocene, the specimen from the Lower Miocene has a wider umbilicus. *C. lapugyensis* Janssen, 2004 from the Middle Miocene of the Paratethys, regarded as descended from *C. praelapugyensis*, is very similar. However, *C. praelapugyensis* is distinguished by the less numerous cords. In *C. lapugyensis*, the body whorl bears two additional cords, one at the shoulder and one at the third abapical part of the whorl.

Clatrosansonia lapugyensis Janssen, 2004 (Fig. 4N)

Clatrosansonia lapugyensis Janssen, 2004: 172, pl. 3 fig. 8-9.

Material examined: ROMANIA • 1 spm. (*paratype*); Lapugy; Middle Miocene, Badenian; SMF 306364. This Badenian species was described from three damaged shells.

Genus *Chrystella* Laseron, 1957

Type species *Chrystella islandica* Laseron, 1957 (by original designation): Recent, Christmas I. In Europe, this genus is known only in the Badenian series.

Figure 4. A-F. *Clatrosansonia luporadens* n. sp., Upper Oligocene, Saint-Paul-lès-Dax (Estoti), holotype [MNHN.FA88444], H= 1.2 mm. G-M. *Clatrosansonia praelapugyensis* n. sp. G-I: Upper Oligocene, Saint-Paul-lès-Dax (Bezoye, Falaise), holotype [MNHN.FA88445], Dmax= 0.9 mm; J-M: Upper Burdigalian, Saint-Martin-de-Hinx (Secat) [MNHN.FA88446], Dmax= 0.95 mm. N. *Clatrosansonia lapugyensis* Janssen, 2004, Middle Miocene (Badenian), Romania, Lapugy, paratype [SMF 306364], Dmax= 8.4 mm. SEM micrographs by J. Le Renard (A-M) and S. Hof (N).

Figura 4. A-F *Clatrosansonia luporadens* n. sp., Oligoceno superior, Saint-Paul-lès-Dax (Estoti), holotipo [MNHN.FA88444], H= 1,2 mm. G-M. *Clatrosansonia praelapugyensis* n. sp. G-I: Oligoceno superior, Saint-Paul-lès-Dax (Bezoye, Falaise), holotipo [MNHN.FA88445], Dmax= 0,9 mm; J-M: Burdigaliense superior, Saint-Martin-de-Hinx (Secat) [MNHN.FA88446], Dmax= 0,95 mm. N. *Clatrosansonia lapugyensis* Janssen, 2004, Mioceno medio (Badeniense), Rumania, Lapugy, paratipo [SMF 306364], Dmax= 8,4 mm. Micrografías electrónicas de barrido por J. Le Renard (A-M) and S. Hof (N).

Figure 5. A, B. *Chrystellia steiningeri* Janssen, 2004, holotype, Middle Miocene (Badenian), Romania (Kostej: Parau saraturi) [SMF 306366], H= 1.35 mm. C, D. *Chrystellia tenuilirata* Janssen, 2004 holotype, Middle Miocene (Badenian), Romania (Lapugy: Valea cosului) [SMF 306368] H= 1.27 mm. SEM micrographs by S. Hof.

Figura 5. A, B. *Chrystellia steiningeri* Janssen, 2004, holotipo, Mioceno medio (Badeniense), Rumania (Kostej: Parau saraturi) [SMF 306366], H= 1,35 mm. C, D. *Chrystellia tenuilirata* Janssen, 2004, holotipo, Mioceno medio (Badeniense), Rumania (Lapugy: Valea cosului) [SMF 306368] H= 1,27 mm. Micrografías electrónicas de barrido por S. Hof.

Chrystellia steiningeri Janssen, 2004 (Figs. 5A, B)

Chrystellia steiningeri Janssen, 2004: 174, pl. 4 fig. 10.

Material examined: ROMANIA • 1 spm. (*holotype*); Kostej: Parau saraturi; Middle Miocene, Badenian; SMF 306366. 1 spm. (*paratype*); same data as for holotype; SMF 306367.

Chrystellia tenuilirata Janssen, 2004 (Figs. 5C, D)

Chrystellia tenuilirata Janssen, 2004: 175, pl. 4 fig. 11.

Material examined: ROMANIA • 1 spm. (*holotype*); Lapugy, Valea cosului; Middle Miocene, Badenian; SMF 306368.

Genus *Gania* Bandel & Kowalke, 1997

Type species: *G. carinata* Bandel & Kowalke, 1997 (by original designation), Eocene, France.

The genus *Gania* (Fig. 6) is characterized by its simple and slightly prosocline aperture; consequently, the outer lip is not bordered; the sculpture made up of strong carinae is shared by most species. However, though the characteristic “carinate cord” appears the domi-

nant element of the sculpture, we include in this genus a species with smooth whorls and, tentatively, a species with granulous cords. Thus, the species included in this genus range from heavily keeled, as is the type species, to almost smooth, as is *G. laevi-*

Figure 6. Overview of the *Gania*. A, B: *Gania carinata*, Lower Eocene, Gan (Tuilerie), H= 1.0 mm; C: *Gania fossaroides*, Middle Eocene, Peyrehorade (Trompe), H= 0.95 mm; D: *Gania gougeroti*, Middle Eocene, Baron, H= 0.85 mm; E: *Gania laevigata*, Upper Eocene, St-Lon-lès-Mines (Bignaou), H= 1.8 mm; F: *Gania sp.*, Upper Eocene, Cagnotte (Plaisir), H= 1,25 mm; G: *Gania granulosa*, Upper Eocene, Cauneille (Lasserre), H= 1.5 mm; H: *Gania canhotensis*, Upper Eocene, Cagnotte (Plaisir), H= 0.9 mm; I: *Gania marconensis*, Upper Oligocene, Bélus (Marcon), H= 1.3 mm. SEM micrographs by J. Le Renard.

Figura 6. Vista sintética de las *Gania*. A, B: *Gania carinata*, Eoceno Inferior, Gan (Tuilerie), H= 1,0 mm; C: *Gania fossaroides*, Eoceno medio, Peyrehorade (Trompe), H= 0,95 mm; D: *Gania gougeroti*, Eoceno medio, Baron. H= 0,85 mm; E: *Gania laevigata*, Eoceno superior, St-Lon-lès-Mines (Bignaou) H= 1,8 mm; F: *Gania sp.*, Eoceno superior, Cagnotte (Plaisir), H= 1,25 mm; G: *Gania granulosa*, Eoceno superior, Cauneille (Lasserre), H= 1,5 mm; H: *Gania canhotensis*, Eoceno superior, Cagnotte (Plaisir), H= 0,9 mm; I: *Gania marconensis*, Oligoceno superior, Bélus (Marcon), H= 1,3 mm. Micrografías electrónicas de barrido por J. Le Renard.

gata. As defined here, *Gania* is the largest genus of Pickworthiidae in Europe with 11 species listed below; *Gania* is present in all the Paleogene, from the Lower Eocene to the Upper Oligocene. One species (*G. toriferens*)

has been recorded from the lower part of the Middle Miocene of the Paratethys.

Gania European species are:

- *G. carinata* Bandel & Kowalke, 1997: Lower Eocene (Ypresian)

- *G. fossaroides* n. sp.: Middle Eocene (Lutetian)
- *G. gougeroti* Le Renard, n. sp.: Middle Eocene (Bartonian)
- *G. canhotensis* n. sp. Upper Eocene (Priabonian)
- *G. granulosa* n. sp. Upper Eocene (Priabonian)
- *G. laevigata* n. sp. Upper Eocene (Priabonian)

- *G. priaboniana* n. sp. Upper Eocene (Priabonian)
- *G. marconensis* n. sp. Upper Oligocene (Chattian)
- *G. peirahoradensis* n. sp. Upper Eocene-Upper Oligocene (Chattian)
- *Gania* sp. Upper Eocene (Priabonian)
- *G. toriferens* (Janssen, 2004): Middle Miocene (Badenian)

Gania carinata Bandel & Kowalke, 1997 (Figs. 6A, B, 7A-E)

Gania carinata Bandel & Kowalke, 1997: 15, pl. 5 figs 3, 6.

Gania carinata Bandel & Kowalke – KOWALKE, 1998: 76, pl. 10 figs 7, 9.

Material examined: FRANCE • 25 spm.; Pyrénées-Atlantiques, Gan (Tuilerie); Lower Eocene, Ypresian; Le Renard leg.; MNHN.F.A88450.

Remarks: This species is relatively common in the classic outcrop of Gan. It is characterized by its relatively faint

keels crossed by numerous oblique axial ribs and a strongly canaliculated suture.

Gania gougeroti Le Renard, n. sp. (Figs. 6D, 7F, G)

urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:5946BB7B-4849-418F-8D2C-2178283E0C57

Type material. *Holotype:* FRANCE • 1 spm.; Oise, Baron; Middle Eocene, Bartonian; Le Renard leg.; MNHN.F.A88449.

Type locality and stage: Baron, Oise; Middle Eocene (Bartonian) [Auversian (local Stage)].

Etymology: Dedicated to Louis Gougerot, who introduced the author of this species to the study of fossil micromolluscs.

Description: Shell very small, elongated trochiform, consisting of 3 whorls of teleoconch. Protoconch (very worn in the holotype) bulbous, consisting of approximately 2.5 whorls; protoconch I smooth, protoconch II with a strong spiral cord still visible. Sculpture on spire consisting of two nodulous spiral keels crossed by oblique axial ribs; adapical keel, weak, along the suture; abapical keel, particularly strong, at the third abapical part of the whorl, and separated from the suture by a broad flat canal. Last whorl, particularly

convex, occupies 69% of total length of shell; base with 4 spiral cords of decreasing force. Umbilicus narrow and deep. Aperture rounded, prosocline, with discontinuous peristome and excavated columella; thin outer lip. Microsculpture unknown.

Size (holotype): H= 0.85 mm; Dmax= 0.57 mm.

Remarks: *Gania gougeroti* is so far the only species of Pickworthiidae known from the Paris Basin. The species is close to *G. carinata* but differs by having nodulous cords.

Gania fossaroides n. sp. (Figs. 6C, 8)

urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:F7B615A4-F106-4BD7-91D2-0EE3F55960C4

Figure 7. A-E: *Gania carinata* Bandel & Kowalke, 1997, Lower Eocene, Gan (Tuilerie) [MNHN.FA88450] H= 1.0 mm; F, G: *Gania gougeroti* Le Renard, n. sp., Middle Eocene, Baron, holotype [MNHN.FA88449] H= 0.85 mm; H-J: *Gania* sp., Upper Eocene, Cauneille (Lasserre) [MNHN.FA88451] H= 1.25 mm. SEM micrographs by J. Le Renard.

Figura 7. A-E: *Gania carinata* Bandel & Kowalke, 1997, Eoceno inferior, Gan (Tuilerie) [MNHN.FA88450] H= 1,0 mm; F, G: *Gania gougeroti* Le Renard, n. sp., Eoceno medio, Baron, holotipo [MNHN.FA88449] H= 0,85 mm; H-J: *Gania* sp., Eoceno superior, Cauneille (Lasserre) [MNHN.FA88451] H= 1,25 mm. Micrografías electrónicas de barrido por J. Le Renard.

Type material. *Holotype*: FRANCE • 1 spm.; Landes, Peyrehorade (Trompe); Middle Eocene, Lutetian; Lozouet leg.; MNHN.F.A88452. *Paratypes*: FRANCE • 2 spm.; same data as for holotype; MNHN.F.A88453, MNHN.F.A88454.

Type locality and stage: Peyrehorade (Trompe), Landes; Middle Eocene (Lutetian), nannoplankton zone NP 15 (MARTINI 1971).

Other material examined: FRANCE • 11 spm.; Landes, Peyrehorade (Trompe); Middle Eocene, Lutetian; Lozouet leg.; MNHN.

Etymology: The name alludes to the superficial resemblance with the genus *Fossarus* (Planaxidae).

Description: Shell very small, turbiniform, solid, consisting of 2 whorls of teleoconch. Protoconch bulbous, consisting of approximately 2.5 convex whorls, tilted relative to the axis of the teleoconch, ending in a sinusigera varix; protoconch I smooth; sculpture of protoconch II consisting of 7-8 fine, more or less granulous cords, and tending to unify in three broad spiral cords. Sculpture on the last whorl of the spire with four keels crossed by faint oblique axial ribs. Convex body whorl, occupies 78.6% of total length of shell; base with 5 keels including one large bordering a very broad umbilical depression. Aperture quadrangular, with discontinuous

peristome; outer lip thin, prosocline; columella pouring on the umbilical depression. Micro-sculpture: microscopic granules scattered.

Size (holotype): H= 0.95 mm; Dmax= 0.83 mm.

Remarks: *Gania fossaroides* is the only *Gania* with a quadrangular aperture; it differs also from the other species by having a broad umbilical depression bordered by a large cord and a flattened shell-form. The age of the Trompe outcrop is well fixed stratigraphically by the calcareous nannoplankton on the one hand and by the holoplanktonic molluscs on the other hand (LOZOUET & LE RENARD 2007).

Gania canhotensis n. sp. (Figs. 6H, 9)

urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:7EF5D9F5-A42F-4EC6-901B-F0C523A0F2BF

Type material. *Holotype:* FRANCE • 1 spm.; Landes, Cagnotte (Plaisir); Upper Eocene, Priabonian; Lozouet leg.; MNHN.F.A88447. *Paratype:* FRANCE • 1 spm.; same data as for holotype; MNHN.F.A88448.

Type locality and stage: Cagnotte (Plaisir), Landes; Upper Eocene (Priabonian), "marnes de Brihande".

Etymology: from its type locality Cagnotte, Canhota in the Occitan language.

Description: Shell very small, thin, turbiniform, consisting of 2¹/₄ whorls of teleoconch. Protoconch bulbous, consisting of approximately 2.5 convex whorls, tilted relative to the axis of the teleoconch, ending in a strong sinusigera varix; protoconch I smooth; sculpture of protoconch II consisting of 7-8 very fine more or less granulous cords and tending to unify in two broad spiral ribbons on the adapical part. Sculpture on the last whorl of the spire comprising three keels including one weak along the suture. Convex body whorl, occupies approximately 75% of total length of shell. Base with 5 keels including

one bordering an imperceptible umbilicus. Aperture rounded, with discontinuous, thin peristome; outer lip very fine, prosocline. Micro-sculpture: teleoconch studded by micro-pustules more or less aligned spirally.

Size (holotype): H= 0.93 mm; Dmax= 0.73 mm.

Remarks: The paratype (Figs. 9G-K) shows 4 weaker keels on the base. The shell shape of this species is similar to that of *Gania carinata* from the Ypresian. Otherwise, *Gania canhotensis* differs by having a tiny turbiniform shape and a narrower umbilicus.

Gania granulosa n. sp. (Figs. 6G, 10)

urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:714C7FD3-C2E9-4462-B669-C668253D34CC

Type material. *Holotype:* FRANCE • 1 spm.; Landes, Cauneille (Lasserre); Upper Eocene, Priabonian; Lozouet leg.; MNHN.F.A88455. *Paratypes:* FRANCE • 3 spm.; same data as for holotype; MNHN.F.A88456, MNHN.F.A88457, MNHN.F.A88458 • 1 paratype; same data as for holotype; SMF 373193.

Figure 8. *Gania fossaroides* n. sp., Middle Eocene, Peyrehorade (Trompe). A-E: holotype, [MNHN.FA88452] H= 0.95 mm; F-G: paratype [MNHN.FA88453] H= 1 mm; H-N: paratype [MNHN.FA88454] H= 0.9 mm. SEM micrographs by J. Le Renard.

Figura 8. *Gania fossaroides* n. sp., Eoceno medio, Peyrehorade (Trompe). A-E: holotipo, [MNHN.FA88452] H= 0,95 mm; F-G: paratipo [MNHN.FA88453] H= 1 mm; H-N: paratipo [MNHN.FA88454] H= 0,9 mm. Micrografías electrónicas de barrido por J. Le Renard.

Figure 9. *Gania canhotensis* n. sp. Upper Eocene, Cagnotte (Plaisir). A-D: holotype [MNHN.FA88447], H= 0.9 mm; E-K: paratype [MNHN.FA88448], H= 0.7 mm. SEM micrographs by J. Le Renard.

Figura 9. *Gania canhotensis* n. sp. Eoceno superior, Cagnotte (Plaisir). A-D: holotipo [MNHN.FA88447], H= 0,9 mm; E-K: paratipo [MNHN.FA88448], H= 0,7 mm. Micrografías electrónicas de barrido por J. Le Renard.

Figure 10. *Gania granulosa* n. sp., Upper Eocene, Cauneille (Lasserre). A-E: holotype [MNHN.FA88455] H= 1.5 mm; F, G: paratype [MNHN.FA88456] H= 1.1 mm; H, I: paratype [MNHN.FA88457] H= 0.95 mm.; J-L: paratype [MNHN.FA88458] H= 1.7 mm. SEM micrographs by J. Le Renard.

Figura 10. Gania granulosa n. sp., Eoceno superior, Cauneille (Lasserre). A-E: holotipo [MNHN.FA88455] H= 1,5 mm; F, G: paratipo [MNHN.FA88456] H= 1,1 mm; H, I: paratipo [MNHN.FA88457] H= 0,95 mm; J-L: paratipo [MNHN.FA88458] H= 1,7 mm. Micrografías electrónicas de barrido por J. Le Renard.

Type locality and stage: Cauneille (Lasserre), Landes; Upper Eocene (Priabonian), "couches de Cauneille".

Other material examined: FRANCE • 11 spm.; Landes, Cauneille (Lasserre); Upper Eocene, Priabonian; Lozouet leg.; MNHN • 2 spm.; Landes, Cagnotte (Plaisir); Lozouet leg.; MNHN.

Etymology: Refers to the granulose cords.

Description: Shell very small, trochiform, consisting of 3.5 convex whorls of teleoconch, separated by a channelled suture. Protoconch bulbous, consisting of approximately 2.5 convex whorls, tilted relative to the axis of the teleoconch, ending in a broad sinusigera notch; protoconch I apparently smooth; sculpture of protoconch II consisting of more or less granulous cords, tending to unify as 7-6 cords unequally spaced. Sculpture on the last whorl of the spire consisting of 5 granulous cords with about 20 obscure oblique axial ribs; the adapical keel, very weak, close to the suture; the abapical keel at the lower third of the whorl, particularly strong, separated from the

suture by a broad flat channel. Body whorl, convex, occupies 67% of total length of shell; convex base with 5 fine spiral cords evenly matched, with a narrow umbilical depression. Aperture rounded, with discontinuous peristome; thin, prosocline outer lip and excavated columella. Micro-sculpture: microscopic granules cover the entire shell surface.

Size (holotype): H= 1.53 mm; Dmax= 1.10 mm.

Remarks: *Gania granulosa* differs from the other *Gania* by its sculpture of granulous cords. One of the youngest individuals (Figs. 10H-I) is characterized by a protoconch which is less tilted. It may be another species.

Gania laevigata n. sp (Figs. 6E, 11)

urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:59FBB8B8-0B3C-45D1-9E07-4CE3C1FB2CA2

Type material. *Holotype:* FRANCE • 1 spm.; Landes, St-Lon-lès-Mines (Lespontes); Upper Eocene, Priabonian; Lozouet leg.; MNHN.F.A88459. *Paratypes:* FRANCE • 3 spm.; same data as for holotype; MNHN.F.A88462, MNHN.F.A88461, MNHN.F.A88460 • 1 spm.; same data as for holotype; SMF 373194.

Type locality and stage: St-Lon-lès-Mines (Lespontes), Landes; Upper Eocene (Priabonian), "marnes de Brihande".

Other material examined: FRANCE • 25 spm.; Landes, St-Lon-lès-Mines (Lespontes); Upper Eocene, Priabonian; Lozouet leg.; MNHN.

Etymology: The specific name refers to the lack of macro-sculpture.

Description: Shell very small, with a conical spire, with straight whorls, consisting of 3 whorls, separated by a channelled suture. Protoconch bulbous, slightly tilted relative to the axis of the teleoconch, consisting of approximately 3 convex whorls, ending in a sinusigera varix; protoconch I smooth; sculpture of protoconch II consisting of 6 cords, 5 fine cords occupying the abapical two-thirds, 1 broad cord in adapical position. First half of first teleoconch whorl with a keel in adapical position; sculpture consisting of one flat subsutural cord, very obscure threads and growth lines. Body whorl occupies 67.3% of total length of shell; angular base with an imperceptible umbilicus. Aperture quadrangular, with thin discontinuous peristome; outer lip very fine, prosocline.

Size (holotype): H= 1.83 mm; Dmax= 1.20 mm.

Remarks: This species does not show any evident relationship to other described species. It is the only species of *Gania* without macro-sculpture. In addition, it was collected in a marl of circalittoral to Upper bathyal facies regarded as "deep" (NOLF ET AL. 2002). These marls were probably deposited at a water depth of 100-150m. The mollusc shells from Lespontes are often partly dissolved, except those of the Pickworthiidae. However, this assemblage can be regarded as *in-situ*. This is supported by the lack of evidence of transportation and the shells often have the protoconch. The fauna of these marls does not show any element of a cryptic environment. Because the *Gania* are perfectly preserved (except problems of diagenesis)

Figure 11. *Gania laevigata* n. sp., Upper Eocene, St-Lon-lès-Mines (Bignaou). A, B: holotype, [MNHN.FA88459] H= 1.8 mm; C, D: paratype [MNHN.FA88462] H= 1.9 mm; E, F: paratype [MNHN.FA88461] H= 2.15 mm; G: detail of microsculpture of another specimen; H: another specimen, Dmax= 1.2 mm; I, J: paratype (broken shell) [MNHN.FA88460] H= 0.7 mm [1.8 mm when complete]. SEM micrographs by J. Le Renard.

Figura 11. Gania laevigata n. sp., Eoceno superior, St-Lon-lès-Mines (Bignaou). A, B: holotipo, [MNHN.FA88459] H= 1,8 mm; C, D: paratipo [MNHN.FA88462] H= 1,9 mm; E, F: paratipo [MNHN.FA88461] H= 2,15 mm; G: detalle de la microsculptura de otro ejemplar; H: otro ejemplar, Dmax= 1,2 mm. I, J: paratipo (concha rota) [MNHN.FA88460] H= 0,7 mm [1,8 mm cuando entero]. Micrografías electrónicas de barrido por J. Le Renard.

the assumption that *Gania laevigata* did not live in a cryptic environment but in a deep mud bottom, appears very proba-

ble. Hitherto, no species of Pickworthiidae, Recent or fossil, had been suspected to live in such an environment.

Gania sp. (Figs. 6F, 7H-J)

Material examined: FRANCE • 1 spm.; Landes, Cauneille (Lasserre); Upper Eocene, Priabonian; Lozouet leg.; MNHN.

Remarks: Only one worn shell of this species has been collected. It is close to *G. gougeroti*, another species only known from a single worn specimen, but differs

by a more elongated spire and a closed umbilicus. Additional specimens are required to accurately describe this species.

Gania marconensis n. sp. (Figs. 6I, 12)

urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:03462C53-346D-4649-95F2-9D3480E00779

Type material. *Holotype:* FRANCE • 1 spm.; Landes, Bélus (Marcon); Upper Oligocene, Chattian; Lozouet leg.; MNHN.F.A88463. *Paratypes:* FRANCE • 2 spm.; same data as for holotype; MNHN.F.A88464, MNHN.F.A88465.

Type locality and stage: Bélus (Marcon), Landes; Upper Oligocene (Chattian), marls with *Mio-gypsinoides*.

Other material examined: FRANCE • 1 spm.; Landes, St-Etienne-d'Orthe (R. Verdun); Upper Oligocene, Chattian; Lozouet leg.; MNHN • 1 spm.; Landes, St-Etienne-d'Orthe (Ruisseau de l'Eglise, level D); Upper Oligocene, Chattian; Lozouet leg.; MNHN.

Etymology: From its type locality.

Description: Shell very small, risoiform, with a thick test, consisting of about $3\frac{1}{4}$ whorls of teleoconch. Protoconch bulbous, consisting of approximately 2.5 convex whorls, tilted relative to the axis of the teleoconch, ending in a strong sinusigera varix; protoconch I smooth; sculpture of protoconch II consisting of 6 more or less granulous cords. Teleoconch with sculpture consisting of strong sporadically nodulous keels; two strong keels on the first whorl, three strong keels on the other whorls; keels crossed by very faint growth lines. Body

whorl convex occupies approximately 71% of total length of shell; base with 4 keels including one surrounding a narrow umbilical depression. Aperture quadrangular, with discontinuous peristome, outer lip prosocline with thickened rim. Micro-sculpture: microscopic granules covering the entire shell surface.

Size (holotype): H= 1.3 mm; Dmax= 1.10 mm.

Remarks: Compared with the other *Gania*, *G. marconensis* has a thicker test; otherwise it is characterized by its very strong keels.

Gania group of *G. toriferens*

This group differs from the others species classified as *Gania* by having the same sculpture as that of the group of *Mareleptopoma minor*. However its non-duplicated aperture and its thickened rather than bordered outer lip excluded

this group from the genus *Mareleptopoma*. Finally, this group represents a good link between *Gania* and *Mareleptopoma* and demonstrates how, due to large morphological variability, the recognition of genera in this family is problematic.

Gania peirahoradensis n. sp. (Figs. 13A-K)

urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:AD9DE288-FBE6-4DFC-BF59-EA3887195E9A

Figure 12. *Gania marconensis* n. sp., Upper Oligocene, Bélus (Marcon). A, B: holotype [MNHN.FA88463] H= 1.3 mm; C, D: paratype [MNHN.FA88464] H= 1.27 mm; E-J: paratype [MNHN.FA88465] H= 1.25 mm. SEM micrographs by J. Le Renard.

Figura 12. *Gania marconensis* n. sp., Oligoceno superior, Bélus (Marcon). A, B: holotipo [MNHN.FA88463] H= 1,3 mm; C, D: paratipo [MNHN.FA88464] H= 1,27 mm; E-J: paratipo [MNHN.FA88465] H= 1,25 mm. Micrografías electrónicas de barrido por J. Le Renard.

Type material. *Holotype*: FRANCE • 1 spm.; Landes, Peyrehorade (Peyrère); Upper Oligocene (Chat-tian); Lozouet leg.; MNHN.F.A88466. *Paratype*: FRANCE • 1 spm.; same data as for holotype; MNHN.F.A88467.

Type locality and stage: Peyrehorade (Peyrère), Landes; Upper Oligocene (Chattian), marls with *Miogypsinoides*.

Other material examined: FRANCE • 1 spm.; Landes, Cauneille (Lasserre); Upper Eocene (Pri-abonian); Lozouet leg.; MNHN.

Etymology: from its type locality Peyrehorade, Peira Horada in the Occitan language.

Description: Shell very small, risiform, with a thick test, consisting of about 3 1/4 whorls of teleoconch separated by a broad sutural area. Protoconch bulbous, consisting of approximately 2.5 convex whorls, tilted relative to the axis of the teleoconch, ending in a strong sinusigera varix; protoconch I smooth; sculpture of protoconch II consisting of 6 fine cords; cord 1 along adapical suture, with chevron-shaped markings and granules in spiral series; cords 2 and 3, cords 4 and 5, granulous, in two series at the median part of the whorl; cord 6 granulous, at the abapical part. Sculpture on the spire consisting of two strong spiral cords with very large granules (20-22 granules on the penultimate whorl) crossed by obtuse and oblique axial ribs; lower cord (abapical) more projecting than the upper one; adapical cord along the suture; abapical cord at the lower third of the whorl, separated from the suture by a broad flat channel. The body whorl, convex, occupies 65% of total length of shell. Convex base with 4 keels and a narrow umbilicus. Aperture ovoid, with weak peristome; outer lip prosocline, thickened

with a slightly bordered rim. Microsculpture: teleoconch entirely covered with fine spiral threads, growth lines and scattered micro-granules.

Size (holotype): H= 1.33 mm; Dmax= 0.93 mm.

Remarks: *Gania peirahoradensis* is very close to *G. toriferens* (Janssen, 2004) collected from the Badenian (Middle Miocene). It differs by its sculpture consisting of spiral cords with large spiny granules as of the first whorl of the spire; on *G. toriferens* (Figs. 13L-M), the granules are not as spiny and are quite visible only after the first whorl; in addition, the cords on the base are much stronger in *G. toriferens*. *Gania peirahoradensis* illustrates once again the link between the Upper Oligocene fauna of Peyrère and some assemblages from the Middle Miocene (Badenian) of Paratethys. LOZOUET (2004) hypothesized that it is the presence of cryptic environments and in particular of submarine caves which unifies these fauna. The study of the Brachiopoda fauna has confirmed this view (Bitner *ET AL.* 2013). It should be noted that one specimen was collected in the Upper Eocene.

Gania toriferens (Janssen, 2004) (Figs. 13L-M) new combination

Mareleptopoma toriferens Janssen, 2004: 173, pl. 3 fig. 7.

Material examined: ROMANIA • 1 spm. (*holotype*); Lapugy, Valea cosului; Middle Miocene, Badenian; SMF 306360.

Discussion: As indicated above this species is related to *Gania peirahoradensis* from the Upper Oligocene (Chattian).

Gania priaboniana n. sp. (Fig. 14)

urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:434A508F-D702-4B8E-8A13-D13EC28144E9

(Right page) Figure 13. A-G. *Gania peirahoradensis* n. sp., Upper Oligocene, Peyrehorade (Peyrère). A-C: holotype [MNHN.FA88466] H= 1.3 mm; D-G: paratype [MNHN.FA88467] H= 1.5 mm. H-K, *Gania* cf. *peirahoradensis* n. sp, Upper Eocene, Cauneille (Lasserre) [MNHN.FA88468] H= 1.4 mm. L, M. *Gania toriferens* (Janssen, 2004), Middle Miocene (Badenian), Romania, Lapugy (Valea cosului) [SFM 306360], H= 1.6 mm. SEM micrographs by J. Le Renard (A-K) and S. Hof (L, M).

Figura 13. A-G. *Gania peirahoradensis* n. sp., Oligoceno superior, Peyrehorade (Peyrère). A-C: holotipo [MNHN.FA88466] H= 1,3 mm; D-G: paratipo [MNHN.FA88467] H= 1,5 mm; H-K, *Gania* cf. *peirahoradensis* n. sp., Eoceno superior, Cauneille (Lasserre) [MNHN.FA88468] H= 1,4 mm. L, M. *Gania toriferens* (Janssen, 2004), Mioceno medio (Badeniense), Rumania, Lapugy (Valea cosului) [SFM 306360], H= 1,6 mm. Micrografías electrónicas de barrido por J. Le Renard (A-K) y S. Hof (L, M).

Type material. *Holotype*: FRANCE • 1 spm.; Landes, Cauneille (Lasserre); Upper Eocene (Priabonian); Lozouet leg.; MNHN.F.A88469. *Paratype*: FRANCE • 1 spm.; same data as the holotype; MNHN.F.A88470.

Type locality and stage: Cauneille (Lasserre), Landes; Upper Eocene (Priabonian), “couches de Cauneille”.

Other material examined: FRANCE • 5 spm.; Landes, Cagnotte (Plaisir); Upper Eocene (Priabonian); Lozouet leg.; MNHN.

Etymology: refers to its Geological Stage

Description: Shell very small, rissoiform, thick, consisting of $3\frac{1}{4}$ whorls of teleoconch. Protoconch bulbous, consisting of approximately 2.5 convex whorls, tilted relative to the axis of the teleoconch, ending in a strong sinusigera varix; protoconch I smooth; sculpture of protoconch II consisting of 6 fine cords, not very distinguishable because of wear; cord 1 along adapical suture, with a herringbone pattern; cords 2 and 3, cords 4 and 5, granulous, in two bands in the median part of the whorl; cord 6 granulous at the abapical part. Sculpture on the spire consisting of two spiral cords with about 20 large granules, crossed by obtuse and oblique axial ribs; adapical cord much weaker, close to the suture; abapical cord a little stronger, at the lower third of the whorl, separated from the suture by a broad flat channel. Body whorl convex occu-

pies 61.5% of total length of shell. Convex base with 5 unequal cords with a narrow umbilicus. Aperture ovoid, with weak peristome, outer lip broken. Micro-sculpture: teleoconch entirely covered with micro-granules and growth lines.

Size (holotype): H= 1.3 mm; Dmax= 0.80 mm.

Remarks: *Gania priaboniana* differs from *G. peirahoradensis* n. sp. and *G. toriferens* (Janssen, 2004) (Fig. 13L, M) by the presence of 5 cords on its base and the weaker spiral cords of its teleoconch, in particular, the adapical cord; the nodules in the crossing of cords and axial ribs are also very weak. Compared to the other *Gania*, *Gania priaboniana* has a spire that is more elongated and cords that are more spiny. *Gania* sp. bears also an additional cord between the main cords of the body whorl.

Genus *Mareleptopoma* Moolenbeek & Faber, 1984

Type species: *Mareleptopoma karpatensis* Moolenbeek & Faber, 1984, by original designation (Recent).

This genus comprises the fossil species often named *Sansonia kenneyi* Ladd, 1966 (Miocene of the Pacific, Marshall Islands), and the Recent species close to *M. iredalei* (Bavay, 1921). Compared to *Mareleptopoma karpatensis*, the *Mareleptopoma kenneyi-iredalei* group differs by a high spire, a close umbilicus and a hardly prosocline aperture. Though submarine caves appear the preferred habitat of the Pickworthiidae, *M. iredalei* (Bavay, 1921) has been collected alive (S. Gofas & A. Warén, pers. comm.) deep under layers of stones, at low tide, in an artificial embankment (New Caledonia, Montrouzier Expedition, Touho). Thus it is clear that

Mareleptopoma includes some generalist species with a more opportunistic habitat preference than the other Pickworthiidae. It requires only a tropical rocky shore, and the presence of submarine caves might not be the determinant factor. Darkness is probably the main abiotic condition. This fact can explain why *Mareleptopoma* is by far the most common group of Recent and fossil Pickworthiidae.

The underestimation of intraspecific variability in *Mareleptopoma* has led to introduction of various synonyms. Therefore numerous specimens of the most common species are illustrated here.

Figure 14. *Gania priaboniana* n. sp., Upper Eocene, Cauneille (Lasserre). A-C: paratype [MNHN.FA88470] H= 1.3 mm; D-F: holotype [MNHN.FA88469] H= 1.45 mm. SEM micrographs by J. Le Renard.

Figure 14. Gania priaboniana n. sp., *holotipo*, *Eoceno superior*, *Cauneille* (Lasserre). A-C: *paratipo* [MNHN.FA88470] H= 1,3 mm; D-F: *holotipo* [MNHN.FA88469] H= 1,45 mm. *Micrografías electrónicas de barrido* por J. Le Renard.

Mareleptopoma lychoviense (Krach, 1981) (Figs. 15-20)

Pareuchelus lychoviensis Krach, 1981: 42, pl. 24 fig. 27-28.

Sansonia kenneyi (Ladd, 1966) – BANDEL & KOWALKE, 1997: 14, pl. 5 fig. 1, 4.

Sansonia kenneyi (Ladd, 1966) – KOWALKE, 1998: 75, pl. 10 figs 10-11.

Mareleptopoma lychoviensis (Krach, 1981) – LE RENARD & BOUCHET, 2003: 588.

Mareleptopoma lychoviense (Krach, 1981) – JANSSEN, 2004: 173, pl. 2 figs 5-6.

Mareleptopoma badenicum Janssen, 2004: 172, pl. 2 figs 3-4.

Material examined: FRANCE • 1 spm.; Pyrénées-Atlantiques, Gan (Acot); Lower Eocene (Ypresian); C. Dolin leg.; MNHN • 1 spm.; Peyrehorade (Trompe), Middle Eocene (Lutetian); Lozouet leg.; MNHN • 57 spm.; Cauneille (Lasserre); Upper Eocene (Priabonian); Lozouet leg.; MNHN • 23 spm.; Landes, Cagnotte (Plaisir); Upper Eocene, Priabonian; Lozouet leg.; MNHN • 3 spm.; Landes, Gaas (Espibos); Lower Oligocene, Rupelian; Lozouet leg.; MNHN • 6 spm. Landes, Orist (Carrère); Lower Oligocene, Rupelian; Lozouet leg.; MNHN; Lozouet leg.; MNHN; Upper Oligocene, Chattian; Lozouet leg.; MNHN • 30 spm.; Landes, St-Paul-lès-Dax (Estoti); Upper Oligocene, Chattian; Lozouet leg.; MNHN • 6 spm.; Landes, St-Paul-lès-Dax (Bezoye, Falaise); Upper Oligocene, Chattian; Lozouet leg.; MNHN • 12 spm.; Landes, St-Paul-lès-Dax (Abesse, level B); Upper Oligocene, Chattian; Lozouet leg.; MNHN • 14 spm.; Landes, Pontonx (Mineur); Upper Oligocene, Chattian; Lozouet leg.; MNHN • 1 spm.; Landes, St-Paul-lès-Dax (Lestrilles); Upper Oligocene, Chattian;

Lozouet leg.; MNHN • 1 spm.; Landes, St-Paul-lès-Dax (Abesse, Château); Upper Oligocene, Chattian; Lozouet leg.; MNHN • 177 spm.; Landes, St-Paul-lès-Dax (Bezoye, level B); Upper Oligocene, Chattian; Lozouet leg.; MNHN • 50 spm.; Landes, St-Etienne-d'Orthe (R. de l'Eglise, level A); Upper Oligocene, Chattian; Lozouet leg.; MNHN • 23 spm.; Landes, St-Etienne-d'Orthe (R. de l'Eglise, level B); Upper Oligocene, Chattian; Lozouet leg.; MNHN • 1 spm.; Landes, St-Etienne-d'Orthe (R. de l'Eglise, level C); Upper Oligocene, Chattian; Lozouet leg.; MNHN • 21 spm.; Landes, St-Etienne-d'Orthe (R. de l'Eglise, level D); Upper Oligocene, Chattian; Lozouet leg.; MNHN • 79 spm.; Landes, St-Etienne-d'Orthe (Ruisseau Verdun); Upper Oligocene, Chattian; Lozouet leg.; MNHN • 2 spm.; Landes, St-Etienne-d'Orthe (Lestelle); Upper Oligocene, Chattian; Lozouet leg.; MNHN • 80 spm.; Landes, St-Etienne-d'Orthe (Hondelatte); Upper Oligocene, Chattian; Lozouet leg.; MNHN • 1 spm.; Landes, Bélus (Caoussit); Upper Oligocene, Chattian; Lozouet leg.; MNHN • 50 spm.; Landes, Bélus (Tauziède, level B); Upper Oligocene, Chattian; Lozouet leg.; MNHN • 89 spm.; Landes, Bélus (Marcon); Upper Oligocene, Chattian; Lozouet leg.; MNHN • 400 spm.; Landes, Peyrehorade (Peyrère); Upper Oligocene, Chattian; Lozouet leg.; MNHN • 1 spm.; Lozouet leg.; MNHN; Lower Miocene, Aquitanian; Lozouet leg.; MNHN • 70 spm.; Landes, St-Paul-lès-Dax (Mainot); Lower Miocene, Aquitanian; Lozouet leg.; MNHN; Lower Miocene, Burdigalian; Lozouet leg.; MNHN • 4 spm.; Landes, St-Paul-lès-Dax (Cabanes); Lower Miocene, Burdigalian; Lozouet leg.; MNHN • 8 spm.; Landes, Mimbaste (Le Houze); Lower Miocene, Burdigalian; Lozouet leg.; MNHN • 22 spm.; Landes, St-Jean-de-Marsacq (Lahitet); Lower Miocene, Burdigalian; Lozouet leg.; MNHN • 15 spm.; Landes, St-Martin-de-Hinx (La Montagne); Lower Miocene, Burdigalian; Lozouet leg.; MNHN • 11 spm.; Landes, St-Martin-de-Hinx (Secat); Lower Miocene, Burdigalian; Lozouet leg.; MNHN; Lozouet leg.; MNHN; Middle Miocene, Langhian; Lozouet leg.; MNHN • 1 spm.; Landes, Saubrigues (Tauziets); Middle Miocene, Langhian; Lozouet leg.; MNHN.

Remarks: JANSSEN (2004, 173) considered that the populations from the Oligocene and the Lower Miocene of Aquitaine, represented a new species that differs from *M. badenicum* due to axial ribs that are more spiny and more numerous. JANSSEN (2004) however did not distinguish between *M. lychoviense* and the Aquitaine basin species.

Otherwise, JANSSEN (2004) distinguished *M. badenicum* from *M. lychoviense* due to the fact that *M. lychoviense* has a proportionally higher shell and a smaller number of axial ribs (15-17 versus 17-18). The comparison of 79 specimens (randomly selected adults) from populations from the Upper Eocene (Priabonian), Upper Oligocene (Chattian) and Lower Miocene (Aquitanian and Burdigalian) based on shell parameters of H/B ratio and number of axial ribs (counting on the penultimate whorl) failed to reveal any consistent difference (Table I). The H/B ratio ranged from 1.08 to 1.4 (the specimens of *M. lychoviense* figured by JANSSEN (2004) range from 1.25 to 1.39, the ratio for *M. badenicum* is 1.32), a one-way Anova shows that this parameter does not permit the exclusion of any group ($p > 0.1$). A scatter plot (Fig. 15C) shows that the specimens from the Lower Oligocene

(Rupelian) and Middle Miocene (Langhian) are positioned in the center of the cluster; the only specimen measured from the Middle Eocene (Lutetian) is positioned with a specimen from the Priabonian in the tail of the cluster. Otherwise, it appears that the distribution of the H/B ratio of *M. lychoviense* is unimodal and not divisible into roughly delineated size classes (Fig. 15B). The number of axial ribs ranges from 14 to 18 (the values for *M. badenicum* [17-18] and *M. lychoviense* [15-17] from the Paratethys are completely within this interval; the Anova reveals that the three groups (Eocene, Oligocene and Miocene) differ for this parameter but with weak support ($p > 0.01$). However, the histogram of the number of ribs (Fig. 15A) shows complete overlap between Eocene and Oligocene populations and a very large overlap between Oligocene and Miocene populations.

We have also examined the teleoconch of more than 700 specimens and though we have noted several different morphs, we failed to separate them into different species; we note:

- in the Upper Eocene, some specimens are more elongated (Fig. 16G-J)
- in the Lower Oligocene, one specimen is more spiny (Fig. 18L)

Figure 15. *Mareleptopoma lychoviense* (Krach, 1981). Comparison of 79 specimens from the Upper Eocene (Priabonian), Upper Oligocene (Chattian) and Lower Miocene (Aquitanian and Burdigalian). A: number of ribs; B, C: height/breadth ratio.

Figura 15. *Mareleptopoma lychoviense* (Krach, 1981). Comparación de 79 ejemplares del Eoceno superior (Priaboniense), Oligoceno superior (Chattianense) y Mioceno inferior (Aquitaniense y Burdigaliense). A: número de costillas; B, C: relación altura/anchura.

Table I. Shell measurements of *Mareleptopoma lychoviense*. SH, Shell Height; SB, Shell Breadth; AR, number of axial ribs on the penultimate whorl.

Tabla I. Medidas de conchas de *Mareleptopoma lychoviense*. SH, altura de la concha; SB, ancho; AR, número de costillas axiales de la penúltima vuelta.

	SH	SB	AR
Middle Eocene (1)	0.88	0.64	17
Upper Eocene (18):			
Minimum	0.88	0.64	14
Maximum	1.28	1	18
Mean	1.12	0.83	15.94
Lower Oligocene (1)	1.2	0.88	18
Upper Oligocene (28):			
Minimum	0.92	0.8	14
Maximum	1.68	1.16	18
Mean	1.2	0.90	16.80
Lower Miocene (30):			
Minimum	0.96	0.7	14
Maximum	1.44	1.44	19
Mean	1.19	0.87	16.86
Middle Miocene (1)	1.12	0.84	15

- in the Upper Oligocene, one of the largest specimens reported of this species shows unusual granulous cords with axial ribs extended on the base (Fig. 18A-B) giving a very distinct net mesh on the base.

- in the Lower Miocene, some specimens have a broader body whorl (Fig. 19M-N) and we note the case of a specimen with smooth cords in the last whorl (Fig. 19C-D).

Otherwise, we have seen no difference in the morphology of the protoconch in our specimens from the Eocene to the Lower Miocene; the protoconchs figured by JANSSEN (2004) are also similar to our specimens.

Given that we can find no observable, morphologically consistent differences, we interpret all these populations as belonging to a single, widespread species. In the absence of any clear differentiation between *M. lychoviense* and *M. badenicum*, that occur sympatrically in the Badenian, these species are recognized as synonyms. Thus, such as we

understand it, the species *Mareleptopoma lychoviense* has a stratigraphic range distribution from the Lower Eocene to the Middle Miocene in Europe.

Mareleptopoma minor (Almera & Bofill, 1898) (= *Sansonia italica* Raffi & Taviani, 1985) from the Mediterranean Pliocene (SOSSO ET AL. 2008) seems to be characterized by a broader body whorl than *M. lychoviense* (LANDAU & FORTEA 2006, figs 1-2; ROLÁN 2005, pl. 2 figs 15-17; pl. 3 figs 18, 20), the H/B ratio has a mean of 1.21 (ROLÁN 2005) versus 1.36 for *M. lychoviense* [1.35 for the Eocene populations, 1.34 for the Upper Oligocene, 1.36 for the Lower Miocene]. However, the presence of an additional cord on the base of *Mareleptopoma minor* appears a better differential character. A similar species, *Mareleptopoma defluxum* Rolán, 2005 is known from West Africa (Cape Verde Islands); it is characterized by a narrower spiral angle and by the presence of only 3 cords on its base. This characteristic may indicate a closer relationship with the group of *M. lychoviense*. Compared to *M. lychoviense*,

Figure 16. *Mareleptopoma lychoviense* (Krach, 1981), Upper Eocene (Priabonian). A-C: Cauneille (Lasserre) [MNHN.FA88471] H= 1.1 mm; D-F: Cauneille (Lasserre) [MNHN.FA88472] H= 1.0 mm; G-H, Cagnotte (Plaisir) [MNHN.FA88473] H= 1.2 mm; I: Cagnotte (Plaisir) [MNHN.FA88475] H= 1.2 mm; J: Cagnotte (Plaisir) [MNHN.FA88474] H= 1.15 mm. SEM micrographs by J. Le Renard.

Figura 16. Mareleptopoma lychoviense (Krach, 1981), Eoceno superior (Priabonense). A-C: Cauneille (Lasserre) [MNHN.FA88471] H= 1,1 mm; D-F: Cauneille (Lasserre) [MNHN.FA88472] H= 1.0 mm. G-H, Cagnotte (Plaisir) [MNHN.FA88473] H= 1,2 mm; I: Cagnotte (Plaisir) [MNHN.FA88475] H= 1,2 mm; J: Cagnotte (Plaisir) [MNHN.FA88474] H= 1,15 mm. Micrografías electrónicas de barrido por J. Le Renard.

Mareleptopoma kenneyi (Ladd, 1966) (borehole samples of Middle-Late Miocene age of Eniwetok Atoll, Marshall Islands), has a higher spire. We note that we have not

examined a large enough series of *Mareleptopoma minor*, *Mareleptopoma defluxum* and *Mareleptopoma kenneyi*, so our opinion on the value of these species is subjective.

Figure 17. *Mareleptopoma lychoviense* (Krach, 1981), Upper Oligocene, Peyrehorade (Peyrère). A-C: [MNHN.FA88478] H= 1.25 mm; D, H: [MNHN.FA88480] H= 1 mm; E-G: [MNHN.FA88476] H= 1 mm; I, J: [MNHN.FA88481] H= 1.1 mm; K, L: [MNHN.FA88477] H= 1 mm; M, N: [MNHN.FA88479] H= 1.1 mm. SEM micrographs by J. Le Renard.

Figura 17. *Mareleptopoma lychoviense* (Krach, 1981), Oligoceno superior, Peyrehorade (Peyrère). A-C: [MNHN.FA88478] H= 1,25 mm; D, H [MNHN.FA88480] H= 1 mm; E-G [MNHN.FA88476] H= 1 mm; I, J: [MNHN.FA88481] H= 1,1 mm; K, L: [MNHN.FA88477] H= 1 mm; M, N: [MNHN.FA88479] H= 1,1 mm. Micrografías electrónicas de barrido por J. Le Renard.

Figure 18. *Mareleptopoma lychoviense* (Krach, 1981). A-H. Upper Oligocene, Bélus (Marcon). A, B: [MNHN.FA88482] H= 1.65 mm; C, F: [MNHN.FA88484] H= 1.2 mm; D, E: [MNHN.FA88483] H= 1.4 mm; G, H: [MNHN.FA88485] H= 1.3 mm. I-K. Upper Oligocene, Saint-Paul-lès-Dax (Estoti). I: [MNHN.FA88486] H= 1 mm; J-K: [MNHN.FA88487] H= 1.25 mm. L. Lower Oligocene, Orist [MNHN.FA88488] H= 1.25 mm. SEM micrographs by J. Le Renard.

Figura 18. *Mareleptopoma lychoviense* (Krach, 1981). A-H. Oligoceno superior, Bélus (Marcon). A, B: [MNHN.FA88482] H= 1,65 mm; C, F: [MNHN.FA88484] H= 1,2 mm; D, E: [MNHN.FA88483] H= 1,4 mm; G, H: [MNHN.FA88485] H= 1,3 mm. I-K. Oligoceno superior, Saint-Paul-lès-Dax (Estoti). I: [MNHN.FA88486] H= 1 mm; J-K: [MNHN.FA88487] H= 1,25 mm. L. Oligoceno inferior, Orist [MNHN.FA88488] H= 1,25 mm. Micrografías electrónicas de barrido por J. Le Renard.

Unrelated group

Mareleptopoma orbum n. sp. (Fig. 21)

urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:BB95861B-C348-4FB0-A3E2-BBBC8CFED12A

Type material. *Holotype*: FRANCE • 1 spm.; Landes, Cauneille (Lasserre); Upper Eocene (Priabonian); Lozouet leg.; MNHN.F.A88503. *Paratype*: FRANCE • 1 spm.; same data as for holotype; MNHN.F.A88502 • 1 spm.; same data as for holotype; SMF 373195.

Type locality and stage: Cauneille (Lasserre), Landes; Upper Eocene (Priabonian), “Couches de Cauneilles”.

Other material examined: FRANCE • 8 spm.; same data as for holotype; MNHN • 2 spm.; Landes, Cagnotte (Plaisir); Upper Eocene (Priabonian); Lozouet leg.; MNHN.

Etymology: The specific name (Latin adjective *orbis*, meaning orphan) refers to the fact that this species cannot be included in any group of *Mareleptopoma*.

Description: Shell very small, conical, rissoiform, lengthened, with a thick test, consisting of 5 whorls of teleoconch, separated by a grooved suture. Protoconch (paratype) of about 2.5 whorls, slightly tilted relative to the axis of the teleoconch, ending in a well-marked sinusigera notch; protoconch I smooth; sculpture of protoconch II consisting of at least 8 fine cords tending to be grouped in two main bands. Sculpture on the first and second whorl of the spire consisting of 2 rows of cords with spiny nodules, crossed by 16 opisthocline axial ribs; the first row is located along the adapical suture, the second row along the abapical suture; a third cord appears before the end of the second whorl, coalescent with the abapical cord at the beginning; this cord becomes more pronounced on the penultimate whorl. The three cords

are evenly-spaced on the last whorl and evenly matched. Body whorl occupies 64.5% of total length of shell; base convex, sculptured with three cords, two main cords at the periphery, one faint cord in the median position. Aperture rounded, prosocline, with a continuous peristome; outer lip bordered by a moderate varix. No umbilicus.

Size (holotype): H= 1.6 mm; Dmax= 1.15 mm.

Remarks: Considering its large size, its high spire and the fact that a perfectly preserved adult specimen bears 4 cords on the base, this species cannot be confused with other species of *Mareleptopoma*. We note some similarities with the two European *Microliotia* but these species differ completely by having a broad last whorl and a strongly prosocline aperture bordered by strong rib.

Mareleptopoma? alicae n. sp. (Fig. 22)

urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:755EA98A-46B7-450B-89E5-3D5202BE6F42

(Right page) Figure 19. *Mareleptopoma lychoviense* (Krach, 1981), Lower Miocene. A, E: Aquitanian, St-Paul-lès-Dax (Maïnot) [MNHN.F.A88491] H= 1.5 mm; B: St-Paul-lès-Dax (Maïnot) [MNHN.F.A88492] H= 1.4 mm; C, D: St-Paul-lès-Dax (Maïnot) [MNHN.F.A88489] H= 1 mm; F, G: St-Paul-lès-Dax (Maïnot) [MNHN.F.A88490] H= 1.1 mm; H: Burdigalian, Saint-Paul-lès-Dax (Cabanes) [MNHN.F.A88493] H= 1.35 mm; I: Upper Burdigalian, Saint-Jean-de-Marsacq (Lahitet) [MNHN.F.A88497] H= 1.15 mm; J: Upper Burdigalian, Saint-Martin-de-Hinx (La Montagne) [MNHN.F.A88495] H= 1.2 mm; K: Upper Burdigalian, Saint-Martin-de-Hinx (Lanot) [MNHN.F.A88501] H= 1,1 mm; L: Saint-Martin-de-Hinx (Lanot) [MNHN.F.A88499] H= 1.15 mm; M, N: Burdigalian, Mimbaste (Le Houze) [MNHN.F.A88494] H= 1.25 mm; O: Saint-Jean-de-Marsacq (Lahitet) [MNHN.F.A88498] H= 1 mm. SEM micrographs by J. Le Renard.

Figura 19. *Mareleptopoma lychoviense* (Krach, 1981), Mioceno inferior. A, E: *Aquitaniense*, St-Paul-lès-Dax (Maïnot) [MNHN.FA88491] H= 1,5 mm; B: St-Paul-lès-Dax (Maïnot) [MNHN.FA88492] H= 1,4 mm; C, D: St-Paul-lès-Dax (Maïnot) [MNHN.FA88489] H= 1 mm; F, G: St-Paul-lès-Dax (Maïnot) [MNHN.FA88490] H= 1,1 mm; H: *Burdigaliense*, Saint-Paul-lès-Dax (Cabanes) [MNHN.FA88493] H= 1,35 mm; I: *Burdigaliense superior*, Saint-Jean-de-Marsacq (Labitet) [MNHN.FA88497] H= 1,15 mm; J: *Burdigaliense superior*, Saint-Martin-de-Hinx (La Montagne) [MNHN.FA88495] H= 1,2 mm; K: *Burdigaliense superior*, Saint-Martin-de-Hinx (Lanot) [MNHN.FA88501] H=1,1 mm; L: misma localidad [MNHN.FA88499] H= 1,15 mm; M, N: *Burdigaliense*, Mimbaste (Le Houze) [MNHN.FA88494] H= 1,25 mm; O: misma localidad [MNHN.FA88498] H= 1 mm. Micrografías electrónicas de barrido por J. Le Renard.

Figure 20. Protoconchs of *Mareleptopoma lychoviense* (Krach, 1981). A-F. Upper Oligocene, Peyrehorade (Peyrère). A: [MNHN.FA88479]; B: [MNHN.FA88477]; C: [MNHN.FA88500]; D, E: [MNHN.FA88481]; F: [MNHN.FA88476]. G. Upper Eocene, Cauneille (Lasserre) [MNHN.FA88471]. H, I. Lower Miocene, St-Martin-de-Hinx (La Montagne). H: [MNHN.FA88495], I: [MNHN.FA88496]. SEM micrographs by J. Le Renard.

Figura 20. Protoconchas de Mareleptopoma lychoviense (Krach, 1981). A-F. Oligoceno superior, Peyrehorade (Peyrère). A: [MNHN.FA88479]; B: [MNHN.FA88477]; C: [MNHN.FA88500]; D, E: [MNHN.FA88481]; F: [MNHN.FA88476]. G. Eoceno superior; Cauneille (Lasserre) [MNHN.FA88471]. H, I. Mioceno Inferior; St-Martin-de-Hinx (La Montagne). H: [MNHN.FA88495]; I: [MNHN.FA88496]. Micrografías electrónicas de barrido por J. Le Renard.

Mareleptopoma? sp. – Lauridsen & Schnetler, 2015: 55, fig. 51.

Type material. *Holotype*: DENMARK • 1 spm.; Fakse Quarry; Paleocene (Middle Danian); Schnetler leg.; MGUH-34205. *Paratype*: DENMARK • 1 spm.; same data as for holotype; MGUH-34206.

Type locality and stage: Fakse Quarry, Denmark; Paleocene (Middle Danian), Coral Limestone.

Etymology: dedicated to Mrs Alice Rasmussen, who extensively collected in the type locality.

Figure 21. *Mareleptopoma orbum* n. sp., Upper Eocene (Priabonian), Cauneille (Lasserre). A-F: paratype [MNHN.F.A88502] H= 1.2 mm; G-I: holotype [MNHN.F.A88503] H= 1.6 mm; J: specimen from Cagnotte (Plaisir) [MNHN.F.A88504] H= 1.4 mm; K: same locality [MNHN.F.A88505] H= 1.6 mm. SEM micrographs by J. Le Renard.

Figura 21. *Mareleptopoma orbum* n. sp., Eoceno superior (Priaboniense), Cauneille (Lasserre). A-F: paratipo [MNHN.F.A88502] H= 1,2 mm; G-I: holotipo [MNHN.F.A88503] H= 1,6 mm; J: ejemplar de Cagnotte (Plaisir) [MNHN.F.A88504], H= 1,4 mm; K: misma localidad [MNHN.F.A88505] H= 1,6 mm. Micrografías electrónicas de barrido por J. Le Renard.

Description: Shell very small, conical, rissoiform, thick, consisting of 3 whorls of teleoconch separated by a channelled suture. Protoconch bulbous, consisting of approximately 2.5 convex whorls, tilted relative to the axis of the teleoconch, ending in a sinusigera varix; protoconch II consisting of relatively broad cords not very distinguishable because of wear. Sculpture of the spire consisting of 19 oblique axial ribs with obtuse spiral cords forming rows of nodules at the intersection. Adapical cord along the suture, abapical row of nodules, more prominent at the lower third of the whorl, forming an angulation and sepa-

rated from the suture by a broad flat channel. Convex-angular, body whorl occupies 64.5% of total length of shell. Base bearing 3-4 cords with a deep and narrow umbilicus. Aperture rounded, slightly oblique, with thick peristome; outer lip thickened by a broad varix. Micro-sculpture not preserved.

Size (holotype): H= 1.03 mm; Dmax= 0.80 mm.

Remarks: The sculpture of *Mareleptopoma? alicae* is close to that of the *Mareleptopoma* species. But considering its deep umbilicus and its slightly oblique aperture, the placement of *M.? alicae* in *Mareleptopoma* is questionable.

Genus *Microliotia* Boettger, 1902

Type species: *Microliotia brandenburgi* Boettger, 1902, by original designation (Miocene of Paratethys).

The genus *Microliotia* comprises eleven living species, all from the tropical Pacific (KASE & LETOURNEUX 2013),

and two fossil (Oligocene, Miocene) species from Europe, one of them described below.

Microliotia imperfecta n. sp. (Figs. 23A-D)

urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:F5CABDF7-DDA7-48BC-A699-3FACF35428CB

Type material. *Holotype:* FRANCE • 1 spm.; Landes, St-Paul-lès-Dax (Abesse level B); Upper Oligocene (Chattian); Lozouet leg.; MNHN.F.A88506. *Paratype:* FRANCE • 1 spm.; Bélus (Marcon), Landes; Upper Oligocene (Chattian); Lozouet leg.; MNHN.F.A88529.

Type Locality and stage: St-Paul-lès-Dax (Abesse level B), Landes; Upper Oligocene (Chattian), calcareous sand with *Miogypsinoidea*.

Etymology: The specific name refers to the fact that the shell is broken (incomplete).

Description: Shell very small, conical, trochiform, broad, with very thick test, consisting of at least 4 straight whorls of teleoconch. Protoconch unknown. Sculpture on the spire with 3 cords, crossed by oblique axial riblets; cords and axial riblets forming a regular net with very large tubercles at their intersections. Adapical cord along the suture; one cord in the middle of the whorl; abapical cord separated from the suture by a broad flat canal. The body whorl is angular, very large. Base almost flat, with 6 unequal cords of which one surrounds a narrow umbilical slit. Proso-

cline aperture with thick and duplicated peristome; outer lip thickened by a succession of varices.

Size (holotype): H= 2.5 mm; Dmax= 1.95 mm.

Remarks: *M. imperfecta* is close to *Microliotia brandenburgi* Boettger, 1902 from the Middle Miocene of the Paratethys and has the same very broad shape. It differs by the presence of 3 cords versus 4 in *Microliotia brandenburgi*. In addition, the spiral cords are the dominant sculptural element in *M. imperfecta*, whereas in *Microliotia brandenburgi* the spiral cords dominate only on the body whorl. This results in a regular

Figure 22. *Mareleptopoma? alicae* n. sp., Paleocene, Danian, Fakse Quarry. A, C-E: holotype [MGUH-34205] leg. coll. ISL, H= 1.0 mm; B, F-H: paratype [MGUH-34206] coll. ISL, H= 1.1 mm. SEM micrographs by J. Le Renard.

Figura 22. *Mareleptopoma? alicae* n. sp., Paleoceno, Daniense, cantera Fakse. A, C-E: holotipo [MGUH-34205] rec. col. ISL, H= 1.0 mm. B, F-H: paratipo [MGUH-34206] coll. ISL, H= 1,1 mm. Micrografías electrónicas de barrido por J. Le Renard.

mesh on the entire surface of the teleoconch of *M. imperfecta*; the regular mesh is present only on the last whorl of *Micro-*

liotia brandenburgi. *M. imperfecta* is one of the largest species of the European Pickworthiidae.

Figure 23. A-D. *Microliotia imperfecta* n. sp. Upper Oligocene. A-C: St-Paul-lès-Dax (Abesse B), holotype [MNHN.FA88506] H= 2.5 mm; D: Bélus (Marcon), paratipo [MNHN.FA88529] Dmax= 1.6 mm. E-K. *Microliotia brandenburgi* Boettger, 1902. Middle Miocene, Romania. E-H: Lapugy [MNHN.FJ17615] (coll. Cossmann, leg. Boettger) H= 2 mm, Dmax= 1.5 mm (E); I-K: Lapugy [SMF 325402a] H= 1.8 mm. SEM micrographs by J. Le Renard (A-H) and S. Hof (I-K).
 Figura 23. A-D. *Microliotia imperfecta* n. sp. Oligoceno superior. A-C: St-Paul-lès-Dax (Abesse B), holotipo [MNHN.FA88506] H= 2,5 mm; D: Bélus (Marcon), paratipo [MNHN.FA88529] Dmax= 1,6 mm. E-K. *Microliotia brandenburgi* Boettger, 1902. Mioceno medio, Rumania. E-H: Lapugy [MNHN.FJ17615] (col. Cossmann, leg. Boettger) H= 2 mm, Dmax= 1,5 mm (E); I-K: Lapugy [SMF 325402a] H= 1,8 mm. Micrografías electrónicas de barrido por J. Le Renard (A-H) y S. Hof (I-K).

Figure 24. *Sansonia schnetleri* n. sp. Danian. Fakse Quarry. A-C, G: holotype [MGUH-34207] leg coll. ISL, H= 1.4 mm; D-F, H: paratype [MGUH-34208] leg coll. ISL, H= 1.3 mm. SEM micrographs by J. Le Renard.

Figura 24. *Sansonia schnetleri* n. sp. Daniense. cantera de Fakse. A-C, G: holotipo [MGUH-34207] rec. col. ISL, Al= 1,4 mm; D-F, H: paratipo [MGUH-34208] rec. col. ISL, H= 1,3 mm. Micrografías electrónicas de barrido por J. Le Renard.

Microliotia brandenburgi Boettger, 1902 (Figs. 23E-K)

Microliotia brandenburgi Boettger, 1902: 144.

Microliotia brandenburgi Boettger – COSSMANN, 1921: 17, pl. 1 figs 35-36, pl. 2 figs 96-97.

Microliotia brandenburgi Boettger – ZILCH, 1934: 214, pl. 6 fig. 95a-b.

Microliotia brandenburgi Boettger – TAVIANI & SABELLI, 1982: 545, fig. 6.

Microliotia brandenburgi Boettger – PONDER, 1985: 104, fig. 73C-D.

Microliotia brandenburgi Boettger – JANSSEN, 2004: 171, pl. 1 fig. 1.

Material examined: ROMANIA • 2 spm.; Lapugy; Middle Miocene (Badenian); Boettger leg.; Cossmann collection MNHN.F.J17615, MNHN.F.J17616 • 1 spm.; Kostej (Parau ungurului); Cossmann collection MNHN.F.J03756 <<https://science.mnhn.fr/institution/mnhn/collection/item/j03756>>.

Remarks: This species is clearly related to the Late Oligocene species *Microliotia imperfecta* described in this paper.

Genus *Sansonia* Jousseau, 1892

Type species: *Iphitus tuberculatus* Watson, 1886, by monotypy (Recent).

Sansonia schnetleri n. sp. (Fig. 24)

urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:CCB31FAB-95EA-4D94-AE80-E07804D70B27

Sansonia sp. – Bandel, 1993: 24, pl. 11 fig. 1.

Sansonia hedegaardi Bandel & Kowalke – KOWALKE, 1998: 75, fig. 10; pl. 10 fig. 6 (misidentification).

Sansonia sp. – LAURIDSEN & SCHNETLER, 2015: 55, fig. 50.

Type material. *Holotype:* DENMARK • 1 spm.; Fakse Quarry; Paleocene (Middle Danian); Schnetler leg.; MGUH-34207. *Paratype:* DENMARK • 1 spm; same data as for holotype; MGUH-34208.

Type locality and stage: Fakse Quarry, Denmark; Paleocene (Middle Danian), Coral Limestone.

Etymology: dedicated to Kai Ingemann Schnetler who kindly made his Pickworthiidae specimens available to the author.

Description: Shell small, rissoiform, very broad, with a thick test, consisting of more than 3 convex whorls of teleoconch separated by a grooved suture. Protoconch (not well preserved in holotype but also relatively worn in the paratype) of at least 2 whorls, ending in a well-marked sinusigera notch; sculpture of protoconch II consisting of two main large cords. First teleoconch whorl with 2 cords, one at the adapical part, along the suture, the second at the abapical part; obscure axial ribs on the first whorl, very large on the subsequent whorls. The spiral cords become pro-

gressively less pronounced then obsolete. 18 large oblique ribs in the penultimate whorl. Body whorl convex occupies 71% of total length of shell; base with a smooth cord; no umbiculus. Aperture rounded, prosocline with thick and duplicated peristome; outer lip bordered by a large rib.

Size (holotype): H= 1.4 mm; Dmax= 1 mm.

Remarks: This species, previously confused with *Sansonia? hedegaardi*, is easily separated by its classic prosocline aperture, its protoconch bearing broad cords and its massive shape.

Figure 25. *Sansonia orthensis* n. sp. Upper Eocene (Priabonian), Cauneille (Lasserre). A-D, F: holotype [MNHN.FA88520] H= 1.8 mm; G, H: Cagnotte (Plaisir), paratype [MNHN.FA88524] H= 1.3 mm; E, I: Cauneille (Lasserre), paratype [MNHN.FA88522] H= 1 mm; J: Cagnotte (Plaisir) [MNHN.FA88525] H= 1.5 mm; K, L: Cauneille (Lasserre) [MNHN.FA88521] H= 1.2 mm. SEM micrographs by J. Le Renard.

Figura 25. Sansonia orthensis n. sp. Eoceno superior (Priaboniense), Cauneille (Lasserre). A-D, F: holotipo [MNHN.FA88520] H= 1,8 mm; G, H: Cagnotte (Plaisir), paratipo [MNHN.FA88524] H= 1,3 mm; E, I: Cauneille (Lasserre), paratipo [MNHN.FA88522] H= 1 mm; J: Cagnotte (Plaisir) [MNHN.FA88525] H= 1,5 mm; K, L: Cauneille (Lasserre) [MNHN.FA88521] H= 1,2 mm. Micrografías electrónicas de barrido por J. Le Renard.

Sansonia orthensis n. sp. group

This group is characterized by its flat, almost smooth base, with a strong, smooth cord. It includes *Sansonia orthensis*, *Sansonia aturensis*, *Sansonia imperforata* from the Priabonian and *Sansonia?* sp. from the Lower Oligocene.

Sansonia orthensis n. sp. (Fig. 25)

urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:BE457262-F4AF-4964-9E93-E11537CCEB83

Type material. *Holotype*: FRANCE • 1 spm.; Landes, Cauneille (Lasserre); Upper Eocene (Priabonian); Lozouet leg.; MNHN.F.A88520. *Paratypes*: FRANCE • 3 spm.; same data as for holotype; MNHN.F.A88524, MNHN.F.A88522, MNHN.F.A88523 • 1 spm.; same data as for holotype; SMF 373196.

Type locality and stage: Cauneille (Lasserre), Landes; Upper Eocene (Priabonian), “Couches de Cauneilles”.

Other material examined: FRANCE • 47 spm.; Landes, Cauneille (Lasserre); Upper Eocene (Priabonian); Lozouet leg.; MNHN • 16 spm.; Landes, Cagnotte (Plaisir); Upper Eocene (Priabonian); Lozouet leg.; MNHN.

Etymology: From the “Pays d’Orthe”.

Description: Shell small, very conical, trochiform, very broad, with a thick test, consisting of more than 4 whorls of teleoconch almost straight, sutural zone forming a broad flat canal. Protoconch (not well preserved in holotype but also relatively worn in the paratype) of at least 2 whorls ending in a well-marked sinusigera notch; sculpture of protoconch II consisting of at least 7 fine cords not very distinguishable. Sculpture on the spire with 2 rows of cords with relatively faint tubercles, crossed by 21 strongly prosocline strong axial ribs; rows of tubercles located at the adapical part and at the abapical part along the suture. Body whorl occupies

54% of total length of shell, very angular, with a very large nodulous cord delimiting the base; flat base, sculptured with fine spiral threads, comprising a large smooth cord in median position; another cord, weaker, surrounding an open umbilicus. Aperture rounded, strongly prosocline with thick and duplicated peristome; outer lip bordered by a succession of varices.

Size (holotype): H= 1.77 mm; Dmax= 1.27 mm.

Remarks: This species is easily recognizable by its sculpture consisting of strong oblique ribs and its broad, almost flat base with only one cord. It is the largest species of European *Sansonia*.

Sansonia aturensis n. sp. (Fig. 26)

urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:C700759F-680B-4727-8E5D-EFBBEC93BA77

Type material. *Holotype*: FRANCE • 1 spm.; Landes, Cagnotte (Plaisir); Upper Eocene (Priabonian); Lozouet leg.; MNHN.F.A88518. *Paratypes*: FRANCE • 2 spm.; same data as for holotype; MNHN.F.A88507, MNHN.F.A88508.

Type locality and stage: Cagnotte (Plaisir), Landes; Upper Eocene (Priabonian), “Couches de Cauneilles”.

Other material examined: FRANCE • 6 spm.; Landes, Cauneille (Lasserre); Upper Eocene (Priabonian); Lozouet leg.; MNHN • 60 spm.; Landes, Cagnotte (Plaisir); Upper Eocene (Priabonian); Lozouet leg.; MNHN.

Etymology: From the Adour basin.

Figure 26. *Sansonia aturensis* n. sp., Upper Eocene (Priabonian). A-C: Cauneille (Lasserre), paratype [MNHN.FA88507] H= 1,35 mm; D-G: Cagnotte (Plaisir), paratype [MNHN.FA88508] H= 1 mm; H-N: Cagnotte (Plaisir), holotype [MNHN.FA88518] H= 2,5 mm. SEM micrographs by J. Le Renard. *Figura 26. Sansonia aturensis* n. sp., Eoceno superior (Priaboniense). A-C: Cauneille (Lasserre), paratipo [MNHN.FA88507] H= 1,35 mm. D-G: Cagnotte (Plaisir), paratipo [MNHN.FA88508] H= 1 mm; H-N: Cagnotte (Plaisir), holotipo [MNHN.FA88518] H= 2,5 mm. Micrografías electrónicas de barrido por J. Le Renard.

Figure 27. A-D. *Sansonia imperforata* n. sp., Upper Eocene (Priabonian), Cagnotte (Plaisir), holotype [MNHN.FA88519] H= 1.45 mm. E-G. *Sansonia miocaenica* Janssen, 2004, Middle Miocene (Badenian), Romania, Lapugy (Valea cosului), holotype [SMF 306353] H= 1.2 mm. SEM micrographs by J. Le Renard (A-D) and S. Hof (E-G).

Figura 27. A-D. *Sansonia imperforata* n. sp., Eoceno superior (Priaboniense), Cagnotte (Plaisir), holotipo [MNHN.FA88519] H= 1,45 mm. E-G. *Sansonia miocaenica* Janssen, 2004, Mioceno medio (Badeniense), Rumania: Lapugy: Valea cosului, holotipo [SMF 306353] H= 1,2 mm. Micrografías electrónicas de barrido por J. Le Renard (A-D) y S. Hof (E-G).

Description: Shell very small, conical, trochiform, broad, with a very thick test, consisting of more than 4.5 whorls with a relatively flat teleoconch, separated by a channeled suture. Protoconch (paratype) of at least 2 whorls, tilted relative to the axis of the teleoconch, ending in a well-marked sinusigera; protoconch I smooth; sculpture of protoconch II consisting of at least 7 fine cords including 6 grouped in three bands. Sculpture on the spire consisting of 2 rows of cords with spiny nodules, crossed by 16-17 strong, strongly prosocline axial ribs; rows of nodules in infra and supra-sutural position. Body whorl occupies 60% of total length of shell, angular, with a large nodulous cord delimiting

the base; sculpture consisting of 5 cords: 3 nodulous cords and two smooth cords on the base. Flat base, comprising a large, smooth cord in a median position; another cord surrounding an open umbilicus. Aperture rounded, strongly prosocline with thick and duplicated peristome; outer lip bordered by a varices.

Size (holotype): H= 1.50 mm; Dmax= 1 mm.

Remarks: This species most closely resembles *Sansonia orthensis* from which it can easily be distinguished by its sculpture that comprises an additional cord on the body whorl; in addition, the cords have spiny tubercles. *Sansonia? aturensis* n. sp is also of smaller size.

Figure 28. *Sansonia* sp. Lower Oligocene (Stampian), Orist [MNHN.F.A88526] H= 1.15 mm. SEM micrographs by J. Le Renard.

Figura 28. *Sansonia* sp. Oligoceno inferior (Estampiense), Orist [MNHN.F.A88526] H= 1,15 mm. Micrografías electrónicas de barrido por J. Le Renard.

Sansonia imperforata n. sp. (Figs. 27A-D)

urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:2B83B2BB-EE0A-44F6-89D7-388FCB38D23C

Type material. *Holotype*: FRANCE • 1 spm.; Landes, Cagnotte (Plaisir); Upper Eocene (Priabonian); Lozouet leg.; MNHN.F.A88519. *Paratypes*: FRANCE • 1 spm.; same data as for holotype; MNHN.F.A88530 • 1 spm.; same data as for holotype; SMF 373197.

Type locality and stage: Cagnotte (Plaisir), Landes; Upper Eocene (Priabonian), “Couches de Cauneilles”.

Other material examined: FRANCE • 7 spm.; Landes, Cagnotte (Plaisir); Upper Eocene (Priabonian); Lozouet leg.; MNHN.

Etymology: Alludes to the closed umbilicus.

Description: Shell very small, conical, trochiform, broad, with a very thick test, consisting of 5 whorls of teleoconch rather flats separated by a channelled suture. Protoconch (observed on paratype) of at least 2 whorls, tilted relative to the axis of the teleoconch, ending in a well-marked sinusigera; protoconch I smooth; sculpture of protoconch II consisting of at least 7 fine cords including 6 grouped in three bands. Sculpture on the spire consisting of 2 rows of cords with spiny nodules, crossed by 13 strong, strongly prosocline axial ribs; rows of nodules in infra and supratural position. Body whorl occupies 54% of total length of shell, angular, with a large nodulous cord delimiting the base; sculpture consisting of 5 cords: 3 nodulous cords and two smooth cords

on the base. Plane base, comprising a large, smooth cord in a median position; another cord surrounds a close umbilicus. Aperture rounded, strongly prosocline with thick and duplicated peristome; outer lip bordered by a varix.

Size (holotype): H= 1.45 mm; Dmax= 0.93 mm.

Remarks: This species is collected associated with *Sansonia aturensis* and, despite resemblance between the two, is treated as a distinct species. However, it is clear that they belong to the same species group. *Sansonia imperforata* is separated by its sculpture that comprises large nodules; the spiral cord delimiting the base is also more nodulous. The spire of *Sansonia imperforata* is also higher and conical, the umbilicus is closed.

Figure 29. *Sansonia? hedegaardi* Bandel & Kowalke, 1997. Danian, Fakse Quarry. A-D: [MNHN.F.A88527] leg H. Zibrowius 1994, H= 1.4 mm; E-I: [MGUH-34209] coll. K.I. Schnetler. SEM micrographs by J. Le Renard.

Figura 29. *Sansonia? hedegaardi* Bandel & Kowalke, 1997. Daniense, cantera de Fakse. A-D: [MNHN.F.A88527] rec. H. Zibrowius 1994, H= 1,4 mm; E-I: [MGUH-34209] col. K.I. Schnetler. Micrografías electrónicas de barrido por J. Le Renard.

Sansonia miocaenica Janssen, 2004 (Figs. 27E-G)

Sansonia miocaenica Janssen, 2004: 171, pl. 1 fig. 2.

Material examined: Middle Miocene (Badenian): Romania: Lapugy: Valea cosului (Holotype SMF 306353).

Figure 30. *Faxia macrostoma*, Danian, Fakse Quarry, leg coll. K.I. Schnetler. A-C: H= 4.5 mm [MGUH-34210]; D, E: H= 3.1 mm [MGUH-34211]; F, G: H= 5 mm [MGUH-34212.]. SEM micrographs by J. Le Renard.

Figura 30. *Faxia macrostoma*, Daniense, cantera de Fakse, rec. y col. K.I. Schnetler. A-C: H= 4.5 mm [MGUH-34210]. D, E: H= 3,1 mm [MGUH-34211]. F, G: H= 5 mm [MGUH-34212.]. Micrografías electrónicas de barrido por J. Le Renard.

Sansonia sp. (Fig. 28)

Material examined: Lower Oligocene: Orist, Landes, 1 spm.

Remarks: This species of the group *Sansonia orthensis*, it is very close to *Sansonia? aturensis*, however its cords have

spiny tubercles. We place this species in open nomenclature pending new material.

Sansonia? hedegaardi Bandel & Kowalke, 1997 (Fig. 29)

Sansonia hedegaardi Bandel & Kowalke, 1997: 14, pl. 5 fig. 2-5.

Sansonia hedegaardi Bandel & Kowalke – LAURIDSEN & SCHNETLER, 2015: 55, fig. 49.

Material examined: DENMARK • 17 spm.; Fakse Quarry; Paleocene (Danian); Schnetler leg; coll. ISL • 1 spm.; Fakse Quarry; Paleocene (Danian); Zibrowius leg; MNHN.F.A88527.

Remarks: This species is unusual among the Pickworthiidae due to its aperture tending to be orthocone. However, the

duplicated peristome of the aperture and the morphology of the protoconch are characteristics of the family.

Subfamily SHERBORNIINAE Iredale, 1917 [= Faxiidae Ravn, 1933]

Genus *Faxia* Ravn, 1933

Type species: *Faxia macrostoma* Ravn, 1933, by original designation (Paleocene, Denmark).

Faxia macrostoma Ravn, 1933 (Fig. 30)

Faxia macrostoma Ravn, 1933: 43, fig. 9-11.

Faxia macrostoma Ravn, 1933 - LAURIDSEN & SCHNETLER, 2015: 56, fig. 54.

Material examined: DENMARK • 150 spm.; Fakse Quarry; Paleocene (Danian); coll. S.B. Andersen • 19 spm.; Fakse Quarry; Paleocene (Danian); coll. A. Rasmussen.

Remarks: LAURIDSEN & SCHNETLER (2015) point that adult specimens with a

complete aperture are rare but the juvenile specimens are common.

DISCUSSION

Biodiversity

Here, 32 species of Pickworthiidae are reported (Fig. 32 and Table II) from Cainozoic deposits (31 from European deposits, one from American deposits). At present, at least 70 living species of Pickworthiidae are known (LE RENARD & BOUCHET 2003; MOOLENBEEK & HOENSELAAR 2010, KASE & LETOURNEUX 2013, KASE & RAINES 2017, TRÖNDLE 2010, ESPINOSA *ET AL.* 2008, POPPE *ET AL.* 2018, MOLLUSCABASE 2023). The majority of the species do not show considerable intraspecific variation and the number of spiral cords on the teleoconch appears to be a very stable character. Inferred from the protoconch morphology (slightly tilted protoconch with a deep sinusigera notch in protoconch II), all the species had a planktotrophic development.

With 10 species, the genus *Gania* is the most diversified. An exceptionally high number of Pickworthiidae (14 species) have been recorded in the North Pyrenean Trough (Eocene) and in a paleo-canyon (Oligocene-Neogene) of the Adour basin. This probably reflects the habitat preference of the Pickworthiidae for cryptic environments and par-

ticularly submarine caves. The presence of such habitats has been demonstrated in the Upper Oligocene (BITNER *ET AL.* 2013) and clearly suspected in the Lower Miocene and Eocene (LOZOUET 2004; LOZOUET & MOLODTSOVA 2008). Otherwise, the fact that one Eocene species (*Gania laevigata*) is strongly suspected to live in relatively deep muddy environment sheds new light on the ecology of Pickworthiidae. The ecology of living species may be much more restricted than in Tertiary times. One species, *Mareleptopoma lychoviense*, represents 74% of the recorded specimens. It is close to *Mareleptopoma iredalei*, the most abundant Recent species of Pickworthiidae (LE RENARD & BOUCHET 2003). These species form a group that is probably more generalist than most of the other Pickworthiidae. *Mareleptopoma lychoviense* is recognized from the Lower Eocene to Middle Miocene. The long-time duration of this species is comparable to that recognized (BEU 1989) for *Charonia lampas* (Linnaeus, 1758). Both species have a planktotrophic larval development with probably a long pelagic-life stage. We note also that,

Table 2. List of European fossil Pickworthiidae.
Tabla 2. Lista de los Pickworthiidae fósiles europeos.

<i>Astrosansonia micraster</i> (Boettger, 1907) Lower - Middle Miocene	<i>Mareleptopoma minor</i> (Almera & Bofill, 1898) Pliocene
<i>Clatrosansonia lapugyensis</i> Janssen, 2004 Middle Miocene (Badenian)	<i>Mareleptopoma lychoviense</i> (Krach, 1981) Paleogene-Neogene
<i>Clatrosansonia luparadensis</i> n. sp. Upper Oligocene	<i>Mareleptopoma orbum</i> n. sp. Upper Eocene (Priabonian)
<i>Clatrosansonia praelapugyensis</i> n. sp. Upper Oligocene	<i>Mareleptopoma? aliceae</i> n. sp. Paleocene (Danian)
<i>Chrystella steiningeri</i> Janssen, 2004 Middle Miocene (Badenian)	<i>Microliotia brandenburgi</i> Boettger, 1902 Middle Miocene (Badenian)
<i>Chrystella tenuilirata</i> Janssen, 2004 Middle Miocene (Badenian)	<i>Microliotia imperfecta</i> n. sp. Upper Oligocene
<i>Gania carinata</i> Bandel & Kowalke, 1997 Lower Eocene (Ypresian)	<i>Sansonia? orthensis</i> n. sp. Upper Eocene (Priabonian)
<i>Gania gougeroti</i> Le Renard, n. sp. Middle Eocene (Bartonian)	<i>Sansonia aturenis</i> n. sp. Upper Eocene (Priabonian)
<i>Gania granulosa</i> n. sp. Upper Eocene (Priabonian)	<i>Sansonia imperforata</i> n. sp. Upper Eocene (Priabonian)
<i>Gania fossaroides</i> n. sp. Middle Eocene (Lutetian)	<i>Sansonia</i> sp. Lower Oligocene (Rupelian)
<i>Gania laevigata</i> n. sp. Upper Eocene (Priabonian)	<i>Sansonia? hedegaardi</i> Bandel & Kowalke, 1997 Paleocene (Danian)
<i>Gania canhotensis</i> n. sp. Upper Eocene (Priabonian)	<i>Sansonia schnetteri</i> n. sp. Paleocene (Danian)
<i>Gania marconensis</i> n. sp. Upper Oligocene	<i>Sansonia miocaenica</i> Janssen, 2004 Middle Miocene (Badenian)
<i>Gania</i> sp. Upper Eocene (Priabonian)	
<i>Gania priaboniana</i> n. sp. Upper Eocene (Priabonian)	<i>Faxia macrostoma</i> Ravn, 1933 Paleocene (Danian)
<i>Gania peirahradensis</i> n. sp. Upper Eocene-Upper Oligocene	
<i>Gania tariferens</i> Janssen, 2004 Middle Miocene (Badenian)	

along with *Sansonia*, the genus *Mareleptopoma* is the only living genus of Pickworthiidae undoubtedly identifiable since the beginning of the Tertiary. Furthermore, as indicated by two worn shells collected in the Lower Miocene of Florida (Chipola formation), *Mareleptopoma* (Fig. 31) occurs during the Cenozoic on both sides of the Atlantic Ocean. This confirms the ubiquity of the group.

Bias in the records of Pickworthiidae

Until now, the Pickworthiidae of the Early Badenian were considered as very original and interpreted as a consequence of an exclusive seaway with the pre-Indo-West Pacific (JANSSEN 2004). Actually, only two species of *Chrystella* and one *Sansonia* appear not directly related to any species from the Aquitaine basin. The Early Badenian is very close in time to the Upper Burdigalian of the Aquitaine basin. This slice of time is represented principally in the Aquitaine basin by the marl deposits of

the paleo-canyon of Saubrigues, it sometimes contains very fine layers with remains of cryptic environments. The Pickworthiidae collected in these layers are transported downslope and are rare; only a single specimen of *Clathrosansonia praelapugyensis* n. sp. has been collected. Therefore, the hypothesis that special feature of Badenian Pickworthiidae is a collecting artefact cannot be excluded. If we consider the stratigraphic range of Pickworthiidae (Fig. 32) it is a succession of disappearances and reappearances, i.e. a good example of the Lazarus effect (FLESSA & JABLONSKI 1983; RAUP 1987) and therefore of the incompleteness of the fossil records. Evidently, these species or genera did not go extinct but something occurred that prevented their preservation. In fact, it is also (or primarily) a consequence of the ecology of this group, mainly restricted to a cryptic environment, that the original habitat is rarely preserved. Another illustration of this collecting artefact is the fact that we do

Figure 31. *Mareleptopoma* sp. Lower Miocene, Chipola Formation (Florida) [MNHN.F.A88528] H= 1.2 mm.

Figura 31. *Mareleptopoma* sp. Mioceno Inferior, Formación Chipola (Florida) [MNHN.F.A88528] H= 1,2 mm.

not know species of Pickworthiidae from the Paleogene and Neogene of the Paleo-Mediterranean. Only two species are reported from the Lutetian (Middle Eocene) that contains, however, one of the most diverse mollusc faunas. In contrast, 4 species are known from only one Paleocene outcrop and 11 species from the Priabonian of a very restricted area.

Climatic constraints

From another point of view, the quasi-absence of the Pickworthiidae from the Paleogene of the Paris Basin, Loire Basin, and Normandy Basin (1 specimen collected) and the absence in the classic outcrops from the Neogene of North Aquitaine (Aquitanian, Burdigalian) indicates probably more a biogeographic pattern than gaps in fossil records. In a global view of the evolution of the European Cenozoic fauna from Oligocene until Recent times, the Pickworthiidae is one of the pan-tropical groups that dramatically suffers from the cooling events of the second part of the Middle Miocene (Serravalian). The only species (*Mareleptopoma defluxum* Rolán, 2005) reported today from the Eastern Atlantic comes from

the West-African province (Cape Verde Archipelago); considering the protoconch morphology the allocation of *Mareleptopoma verdense* Rolán & Rubio, 1999 (reassigned to the genus *Chrystella* by MOOLENBEEK & MUSSAI 2010) to the family Pickworthiidae is doubtful. The family Anabathridae appears a better placement for this species.

Finally, considering the global rarity of the Pickworthiidae recorded in fossil deposits, these new findings raise the possibility that the Pickworthiidae were at least as diversified in the Paleogene as they are today. The Recent distribution of the group (mainly the Caribbean and Indo-West Pacific), is also further example of the remains of an ancient Tethysian distribution.

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Figure 32. Stratigraphical occurrence of Pickworthiidae studied in this paper (modified from LOZOUET 1998, International Chronostratigraphic Chart from <<https://stratigraphy.org/chart>>).
 Figura 32. Ocurrencia estratigráfica de Pickworthiidae estudiados en este artículo (modificado de LOZOUET 1998; Escala Cronoestratigráfica Internacional de <<https://stratigraphy.org/chart>>).

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